

A Transformation Theory Approach to Hamiltonian Dynamics

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Abstract

Two aspects of a Hamiltonian formulation of classical dynamics are investigated using tensor analysis and canonical transformation theory. Using methods from differential geometry it is shown that Hamilton's equations cannot be written as a single tensor equation for systems with a velocity independent potential. The restrictions placed on Hamilton's equations by requiring a contravariant transformation rule for both the generalized coordinates and conjugate momenta are shown to imply the Lagrangian description of dynamics.

The Poisson Bracket conditions for canonical transformations are then derived by considering transformations in phase space and observing the distinction between the contravariant and covariant transformation rules of the Hamiltonian variables.

The Modified Euler, Heun's and Midpoint second order *explicit* Runge-Kutta numerical integration algorithms are analyzed using the Poisson Bracket conditions for canonical transformations, and by using series expansions of the Hamiltonian function $H(Q, P)$. The algorithms are shown to be *canonical* to a specified order of accuracy but *non-symplectic* for a general Hamiltonian function with a single degree of freedom in coordinate space. The order to which the methods do not conserve energy and do not preserve the Hamiltonian structure is compared with the local truncation error for each of the methods.

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2 A Geometric Approach To Classical Dynamics

2.1 Lagrangian Mechanics

Kinetic Energy

Classical dynamics can be formulated from the viewpoint of differential geometry if one first considers the fundamental quadratic form

$$ds^2 = g_{ij} d\xi^i d\xi^j, \quad (2.1.1)$$

defining an element of distance ds on a Riemannian manifold V_N . The fundamental or metric tensor g_{ij} is symmetric, i.e. $g_{ij} = g_{ji}$, and non-singular by the definition of a Riemannian space [5] and $d\xi^i, d\xi^j$ are the curvilinear coordinate differentials. Specializing to V_3 we see that g_{ij} has the signature $(+, +, +)$, so the quadratic form is positive definite.

Eq. (2.1.1) contains two notational devices that will be used extensively. Repeated indices occurring in an upper/lower combination imply summation (Einstein sum convention) while upper and lower indices indicate contravariant and covariant quantities respectively. A contravariant vector A^i is defined by the transformation rule

$$A'^i = \frac{\partial \xi'^i}{\partial \xi^j} A^j, \quad (2.1.2)$$

relating the new components to the old under a transformation of coordinates $\xi^k \rightarrow \xi'^i$. A covariant vector is defined by

$$B'_i = \frac{\partial \xi^j}{\partial \xi'^i} B_j. \quad (2.1.3)$$

Eqs. (2.1.2) and (2.1.3) define contravariant and covariant vectors (tensors of rank one) but are easily extended to tensors of higher rank.

Consider a point mass m moving along a trajectory defined by the curve s . Substituting

$d\xi^i = \frac{d\xi^i}{dt} dt$ into (2.1.1) gives

$$ds^2 = g_{ij} \frac{d\xi^i}{dt} \frac{d\xi^j}{dt} (dt)^2, \quad (2.1.4)$$

so that

$$v^2 = \left(\frac{ds}{dt} \right)^2 = g_{ij} \dot{\xi}^i \dot{\xi}^j. \quad (2.1.5)$$

The kinetic energy of the mass is then

$$T = \frac{1}{2} m v^2 = \frac{1}{2} m g_{ij} \dot{\xi}^i \dot{\xi}^j, \quad (2.1.6)$$

or in Cartesian coordinates

$$T = \frac{1}{2} m \delta_{ij} \dot{x}^i \dot{x}^j, \quad (2.1.7)$$

where δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta defined by $\delta_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & i = j \\ 0, & i \neq j \end{cases}$. For a system of N particles, the kinetic energy is

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^N m_n \delta_{ij} \dot{x}_n^i \dot{x}_n^j, \quad (2.1.8)$$

where the sub-subscript n is used to distinguish individual particles and the summation over i and j will range over (1, 2, 3) in three dimensions or over (1, 2) if we are considering planar motion.

If the system is free from constraints, there are $3N$ independent coordinates or *degrees of freedom* specifying a system configuration. Consider the specific case of a holonomic system, that is one containing d constraint equations

$$f_m(x_1^1, x_1^2, x_1^3, \dots, x_N^1, x_N^2, x_N^3) - c_m = 0, \quad m = 1, 2, \dots, d \quad (2.1.9)$$

where the c_m are constants. We may use the constraints to eliminate d of the $3N$ coordinates leaving $3N-d$ independent coordinates. This elimination of the dependent coordinates can be expressed in

another way by introducing a coordinate transformation from x_n^i to $3N-d$ new independent variables q^j . In principle, all redundant coordinates can be eliminated allowing the number of degrees of freedom to be equal to the number of coordinates in the new generalized set q^j . If $d = 2N$ the transformation equations then take the form

$$x_n^i = x_n^i(q^1, q^2, \dots, q^N). \quad (2.1.10)$$

Differentiating (2.1.10) with respect to t we find that the velocity transforms contravariantly in going from Cartesian to the generalized coordinates:

$$\dot{x}_n^i = \frac{\partial x_n^i}{\partial q^k} \dot{q}^k. \quad (2.1.11)$$

Substituting (2.1.11) into (2.1.8) gives the kinetic energy in terms of the generalized velocities:

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^N m_n g_{kl} \dot{q}^k \dot{q}^l, \quad (2.1.12)$$

where

$$g_{kl} = \delta_{ij} \frac{\partial x_n^i}{\partial q^k} \frac{\partial x_n^j}{\partial q^l} = \frac{\partial x_n^i}{\partial q^k} \frac{\partial x_n^i}{\partial q^l}. \quad (2.1.13)$$

The kinetic energy can now be written more compactly as

$$T = \frac{1}{2} a_{kl} \dot{q}^k \dot{q}^l, \quad (2.1.14)$$

with

$$a_{kl} = \sum_{n=1}^N m_n g_{kl}. \quad (2.1.15)$$

Since T is an invariant under all transformations of generalized coordinates, we must have

$$T = T' = \frac{1}{2} a_{kl} \dot{q}^k \dot{q}^l = \frac{1}{2} a'_{ij} \dot{q}'^i \dot{q}'^j. \quad (2.1.16)$$

After substituting for \dot{q}^k and \dot{q}^l from the coordinate transformation, $q^k \rightarrow q'^j$, we get

$$a_{kl} \frac{\partial q^k}{\partial q'^i} \frac{\partial q^l}{\partial q'^j} \dot{q}'^i \dot{q}'^j = a'_{ij} \dot{q}'^i \dot{q}'^j, \quad (2.1.17)$$

where

$$a'_{ij} = \frac{\partial q^k}{\partial q'^i} \frac{\partial q^l}{\partial q'^j} a_{kl}, \quad (2.1.18)$$

showing that a_{kl} is a covariant symmetric tensor of rank two.

The Kinematic Line Element

If we consider a particle trajectory defining a curve in space parametrized by the time coordinate t , then we can define along this curve a parallel field of velocity vectors having equal magnitude and direction displaced from some arbitrary initial and final points along the curve. Our object is to find the equations that such a vector field must satisfy. For reference, we follow a derivation given by McConnell [23] particularly in obtaining (2.1.23) from (2.1.22).

In the previous section we saw that under the transformation of coordinates $x^i \rightarrow q^i$, the velocity transforms contravariantly by (2.1.11). If there are no external forces, the derivatives of \dot{x}^i with respect to t in Cartesian coordinates are zero. Considering a single particle with no constraints, and then differentiating (2.1.11) with respect to t along the curve, (the indices have been changed from i to r and from k to j) gives

$$\frac{d\dot{x}^r}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial x^r}{\partial q^j} \dot{q}^j \right) = \ddot{q}^j \frac{\partial x^r}{\partial q^j} + \frac{\partial^2 x^r}{\partial q^j \partial q^k} \dot{q}^j \dot{q}^k = 0. \quad (2.1.19)$$

Combining (2.1.13) and (2.1.15) allows us to write

$$a_{jk} = m \frac{\partial x^r}{\partial q^j} \frac{\partial x_r}{\partial q^k}. \quad (2.1.20)$$

and after substituting $\frac{\partial x^r}{\partial q^j} = \delta^{rs} \frac{a_{jk} \partial q^k}{m \partial x^s}$ obtained from the above into (2.1.19) and then multiplying by

$a^{ii} \frac{\partial x^r}{\partial q^i}$ we find that

$$\frac{1}{m} \ddot{q}^l + a^{ii} \frac{\partial^2 x^r}{\partial q^j \partial q^k} \frac{\partial x^r}{\partial q^i} \dot{q}^j \dot{q}^k = 0. \quad (2.1.21)$$

Considering the expression $\frac{\partial^2 x^r}{\partial q^j \partial q^k} \frac{\partial x^r}{\partial q^i}$, we first differentiate (2.1.20) with respect to q^i to get

$$\frac{\partial a_{jk}}{\partial q^i} = m \left(\frac{\partial^2 x^r}{\partial q^j \partial q^i} \frac{\partial x^r}{\partial q^k} + \frac{\partial x^r}{\partial q^j} \frac{\partial^2 x^r}{\partial q^i \partial q^k} \right). \quad (2.1.22)$$

Adding the two equations obtained from the above by permuting l, k, r cyclically and then subtracting (2.1.22) from the result gives

$$\frac{1}{m} \left(\frac{\partial a_{ji}}{\partial q^k} + \frac{\partial a_{ki}}{\partial q^j} - \frac{\partial a_{jk}}{\partial q^i} \right) = \frac{2}{m} [jk, i] = 2 \frac{\partial^2 \dot{x}^r}{\partial q^j \partial q^k} \frac{\partial \dot{x}^r}{\partial q^i}, \quad (2.1.23)$$

where we have shortened our notation by using

$$[jk, i] = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial a_{ji}}{\partial q^k} + \frac{\partial a_{ki}}{\partial q^j} - \frac{\partial a_{jk}}{\partial q^i} \right). \quad (2.1.24)$$

Substituting (2.1.23) into (2.1.21) gives

$$\frac{1}{m} \left(\ddot{q}^l + a^{ii} [jk, i] \dot{q}^j \dot{q}^k \right) = 0, \quad (2.1.25)$$

and if we further write

$$\Gamma_{jk}^l = a^{ii} [jk, i], \quad (2.1.26)$$

(2.1.19) takes the final form

$$\ddot{q}^l + \Gamma_{jk}^l \dot{q}^j \dot{q}^k = 0. \quad (2.1.27)$$

The definitions made in (2.1.24) and (2.1.26) define the *Christoffel symbols* [24] of the first and second kind respectively.

If the parameter t is chosen to be the arc length s of a curve in Riemannian space with metric tensor a_{ii} , then (2.1.27) defines a geodesic [25] in what is known as the *manifold of configurations* [23] which we designate as V_N . Solutions to (2.1.27) are given by

$$q^i = q^i(s) = q^i(t), \quad (2.1.28)$$

and trace out curves defining a surface in configuration space. A distance element ds measured between the points q^i and $q^i + dq^i$ along a curve is called the *kinematical line element* [23] to distinguish it from another given in Appendix A. By analogy with (2.1.1) we then have for ds :

$$ds^2 = a_{ii} dq^i dq^i. \quad (2.1.29)$$

We are led to the same geometrical interpretation if instead of (2.1.11) we start with the Lagrangian equations of motion

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial \dot{q}^i} \right) - \frac{\partial T}{\partial q^i} = F_i, \quad (2.1.30)$$

where F_i is the generalized force defined for conservative systems by $F_i = -\frac{\partial V}{\partial q^i}$. After substituting

$T = \frac{1}{2} a_{ij} \dot{q}^i \dot{q}^j$ from (2.1.14) we have for each of the terms on the LHS:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial T}{\partial \dot{q}^i} &= \frac{1}{2} (a_{ij} \dot{q}^j + a_{ij} \dot{q}^i \delta_i^j) = a_{ij} \dot{q}^j \\ \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial \dot{q}^i} \right) &= a_{ij} \ddot{q}^j + \frac{\partial a_{ij}}{\partial q^k} \dot{q}^k \dot{q}^j \\ \frac{\partial T}{\partial q^i} &= \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial a_{kj}}{\partial q^i} \dot{q}^k \dot{q}^j. \end{aligned} \quad (2.1.31)$$

Eq. (2.1.30) is then

$$a_{ij} \ddot{q}^j + \frac{\partial a_{ij}}{\partial q^k} \dot{q}^k \dot{q}^j - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial a_{kj}}{\partial q^i} \dot{q}^k \dot{q}^j = F_i. \quad (2.1.32)$$

Since the summation over the quadratic form $\dot{q}^j \dot{q}^k$ will give a symmetric result, we can *mix* the indices j and k to obtain for the middle term on the LHS:

$$\frac{\partial a_{(|i|j|k)}}{\partial q^k} \dot{q}^k \dot{q}^j = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial a_{ji}}{\partial q^k} + \frac{\partial a_{ki}}{\partial q^j} \right) \dot{q}^k \dot{q}^j. \quad (2.1.33)$$

(The mixing operation [7] is defined on p indices by adding $p!$ isomers formed by permuting the indices in all possible ways and then dividing by $p!$. Indices involved in the operation are enclosed by $()$ and indices to be excluded are surrounded with $| \cdot |$.)

Substituting (2.1.33) back into (2.1.32):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial \dot{q}^i} \right) - \frac{\partial T}{\partial q^i} &= a_{ij} \ddot{q}^j + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial a_{ji}}{\partial q^k} + \frac{\partial a_{ki}}{\partial q^j} - \frac{\partial a_{jk}}{\partial q^i} \right) \dot{q}^j \dot{q}^k \\ &= a_{ij} \ddot{q}^j + [jk, i] \dot{q}^j \dot{q}^k \\ &= a^{li} a_{ij} \ddot{q}^j + a^{li} [jk, i] \dot{q}^j \dot{q}^k \\ &= \ddot{q}^i + \Gamma_{jk}^i \dot{q}^j \dot{q}^k, \end{aligned} \quad (2.1.34)$$

where we have used the definitions from (2.1.24) and (2.1.26). From (2.1.30) and (2.1.34), we then have

$$\ddot{q}^i + \Gamma_{jk}^i \dot{q}^j \dot{q}^k = a^{li} F_i = -a^{li} \partial_i V, \quad (2.1.35)$$

where $\partial_i \equiv \frac{\partial}{\partial q^i}$ and $F_i = -\partial_i V$, from the definition of a conservative force. If no external forces are acting on the system, we see that (2.1.35) is equivalent to (2.1.27).

It is worthwhile to note that (2.1.35) is simply Newton's Second Law in covariant form. Multiplying both sides of (2.1.35) by a_{lr} gives

$$a_{lr} (\ddot{q}^l + \Gamma_{jk}^l \dot{q}^j \dot{q}^k) = \delta_r^i F_i = F_r, \quad (2.1.36)$$

where the term in parentheses is simply the *covariant derivative* of the velocity vector or the acceleration of the system. If we were to change coordinates from q^i to q'^i , (2.1.36) (or (2.1.35)) would take the identical form in the new coordinate system:

$$a'_{lr} (\ddot{q}'^l + \Gamma'^l_{jk} \dot{q}'^j \dot{q}'^k) = F'_r .$$

where $\Gamma'^l_{jk} = \frac{\partial q'^l}{\partial q^i} \frac{\partial q^r}{\partial q'^j} \frac{\partial q^s}{\partial q'^k} \Gamma^i_{rs} + \frac{\partial^2 q^s}{\partial q'^j \partial q'^k} \frac{\partial q'^l}{\partial q^s}$, and so the Christoffel symbols themselves do not form a tensor quantity.

2.2 Hamiltonian Dynamics

The Hamiltonian formulation does not, in general, decrease the difficulty of solving a given problem in mechanics but rather its usefulness lies in providing a framework for theoretical extensions in other areas of physics. The equal status given to the generalized coordinates and conjugate momenta allows a greater freedom in choosing what physical quantities are to be designated as "coordinates" and "momenta". This greater freedom allows us to construct more abstract representations of physics that are essential to formulating some of the more modern theories of matter [12]. It is through the Hamiltonian procedure that physicists have defined both statistical and quantum mechanics.

In the first part of this section we derive Hamilton's equations starting from Lagrangian mechanics. Next, we pay special attention to the contravariant and covariant transformation laws of the Hamiltonian variables and combine these to derive a contravariant formulation of Hamilton's equations.

Hamilton's Equations

The Hamiltonian description of mechanics is derived by first considering the Lagrangian function, $L = T - V$, which in general has the functional form

$$L = L(q^1, q^2, \dots, q^N; \dot{q}^1, \dot{q}^2, \dots, \dot{q}^N; t), \quad (2.2.1)$$

and define the momentum p_i conjugate to \dot{q}^i by

$$p_i = \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{q}^i}. \quad (2.2.2)$$

Writing the differential

$$dL = \frac{\partial L}{\partial q^i} dq^i + \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{q}^i} d\dot{q}^i + \frac{\partial L}{\partial t} dt, \quad (2.2.3)$$

and then substituting from (2.2.2) gives

$$dL = \frac{\partial L}{\partial q^i} dq^i + p_i d\dot{q}^i + \frac{\partial L}{\partial t} dt. \quad (2.2.4)$$

To express the above equation in terms of the independent variables q^i and p_i we make a Legendre transformation from (q^i, \dot{q}^i, t) to (q^i, p_i, t) by first noting that

$$p_i d\dot{q}^i = d(p_i \dot{q}^i) - \dot{q}^i dp_i.$$

Substituting the above into (2.2.4) we can write

$$dH = d(p_i \dot{q}^i - L) = \dot{q}^i dp_i - \frac{\partial L}{\partial q^i} dq^i - \frac{\partial L}{\partial t} dt, \quad (2.2.5)$$

where

$$H = p_i \dot{q}^i - L, \quad (2.2.6)$$

is defined to be the Hamiltonian. From the Lagrangian equations of motion we have

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{q}^i} \right) = \frac{\partial L}{\partial q^i} = \dot{p}_i, \quad (2.2.7)$$

and if we write dH in the form

$$dH = \frac{\partial H}{\partial q^i} dq^i + \frac{\partial H}{\partial p_i} dp_i + \frac{\partial H}{\partial t} dt , \quad (2.2.8)$$

we see by inspection of (2.2.5), (2.2.7), and (2.2.8) that

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{q}^i &= \frac{\partial H}{\partial p_i} \\ \dot{p}_i &= -\frac{\partial H}{\partial q^i} , \end{aligned} \quad (2.2.9)$$

with

$$\frac{\partial H}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial L}{\partial t} . \quad (2.2.10)$$

The first two equations are Hamilton's equations of motion and the last equation shows that if L is not an explicit function of t then $\frac{\partial H}{\partial t} = 0$, and H is a constant of the motion. The distinction between up and down indices in (2.2.9) establishes the tensor character (contravariant and covariant) under coordinate transformations for the Hamiltonian variables, q^i and p_i , that we use in the next section to investigate a contravariant form of Hamilton's equations.

For systems with a velocity independent potential $\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{q}^i} = \frac{\partial T}{\partial \dot{q}^i}$, and from (2.1.31) and (2.2.2) we

obtain

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial \dot{q}^i} = p_i = a_{ij} \dot{q}^j , \quad (2.2.11)$$

defining p_i as an *associate* vector to \dot{q}^j . Substituting the above into (2.2.6) gives

$$\begin{aligned} H &= a_{ij} \dot{q}^i \dot{q}^j - L \\ &= 2T - (T - V) \\ &= T + V , \end{aligned} \quad (2.2.12)$$

showing that H is the total energy for the system.

Notes On Combining Hamilton's Equations Into A Single Tensor Equation

The hallmark of a Hamiltonian formulation is the symmetry occurring between q^i and p_i in the equations of motion (2.2.9). It therefore seems natural to consider the conjugate coordinates on an equal basis and introduce a single set of $2N$ coordinates ζ^α , where

$$\bar{\zeta} = (q^1, q^2, \dots, q^N, p^1, p^2, \dots, p^N). \quad (2.2.13)$$

In an alternate approach to combining q^i and p_i (known as the *symplectic* [26] formulation of Hamiltonian mechanics) the conjugate coordinates are combined into a single *multiplet* quantity $\bar{\zeta} = (q^1, q^2, \dots, q^N, p_1, p_2, \dots, p_N)$, ignoring the distinction between the contravariant and covariant transformation rules for each of variables.

In the process of obtaining the form of (2.2.13), we are faced with the difficulty of combining the contravariant and covariant variables q^i and p_i into a single contravariant quantity ζ^α . To be consistent we must transform the conjugate momenta p_i into the contravariant form shown in (2.2.13) by raising the index with the inverse of the fundamental tensor a_{ki} , introduced in Section 2.1. We can then write

$$p^j = a^{jk} p_k. \quad (2.2.14)$$

Substituting (2.2.14) into $H = H(q^j, p_j)$ gives (see the discussion in Section 3.1 between (3.1.2) and (3.1.3))

$$H = H'(q^j, a^{jk} p_k) = H'(q^j, p^j), \quad (2.2.15)$$

which we differentiate with respect to p_i to get

$$\frac{\partial H}{\partial p_i} = \frac{\partial H}{\partial p^j} a^{jk} \frac{\partial p_k}{\partial p_i} = a^{jk} \delta_k^i \frac{\partial H}{\partial p^j} = a^{ji} \frac{\partial H}{\partial p^j}. \quad (2.2.16)$$

Since $a^{ji} = a^{ij}$ we write (2.2.16) as

$$\frac{\partial H}{\partial p_i} = a^{ij} \frac{\partial H}{\partial p^j}, \quad (2.2.17)$$

and after substituting the above into (2.2.9) we obtain for the first of Hamilton's equations:

$$\dot{q}^i = a^{ij} \frac{\partial H}{\partial p^j} . \quad (2.2.18)$$

To obtain the contravariant form for the second of Hamilton's equations in (2.2.9) we first multiply \dot{p}_i by a^{li} to get

$$a^{li} \dot{p}_i = - a^{li} \frac{\partial H}{\partial q^i} . \quad (2.2.19)$$

Noting that the LHS of the above can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} a^{li} \dot{p}_i &= \frac{d}{dt} (a^{li} p_i) - \frac{d a^{li}}{dt} p_i \\ &= \dot{p}^l - \frac{d a^{li}}{dt} p_i , \end{aligned} \quad (2.2.20)$$

we then write (2.2.19) as

$$\dot{p}^l = \frac{d a^{li}}{dt} p_i - a^{li} \frac{\partial H}{\partial q^i} . \quad (2.2.21)$$

Writing (2.2.18) and (2.2.21) as a pair of simultaneous equations we get the contravariant form of (2.2.9):

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{q}^l &= a^{li} \frac{\partial H}{\partial p^i} \\ \dot{p}^l &= \frac{d a^{li}}{dt} p_i - a^{li} \frac{\partial H}{\partial q^i} . \end{aligned} \quad (2.2.22)$$

We can now combine \dot{q}^l and \dot{p}^l on the LHS as shown in (2.2.13) to get $\dot{\zeta}^l$. The RHS cannot, however, be written as a single quantity because of the extra term: $\frac{d a^{li}}{dt} p_i$, unless of course $\frac{d a^{li}}{dt} = 0$, which in general, is not true since $a^{li} = a^{li}(q^k(t))$ from (2.1.10) and (2.1.20).

Going back to the second equation in (2.2.22) and using the result from (2.2.12) that $H = T + V$, we write

$$\dot{p}^l = \frac{d a^{li}}{dt} p_i - a^{li} \partial_i (T + V) , \quad (2.2.23)$$

and after substituting $T = \frac{1}{2} a_{rs} p^r p^s$ obtained from combining (2.1.14), (2.2.11), & (2.2.14) we get

$$\dot{p}^i - \frac{d a^{ii}}{dt} p_i + \frac{1}{2} a^{ii} \partial_i (a_{rs} p^r p^s) = - a^{ii} \partial_i V. \quad (2.2.24)$$

Rewriting the last term on the LHS:

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_i (a_{rs} p^r p^s) &= (\partial_i a_{rs}) p^r p^s + a_{rs} [(\partial_i p^r) p^s + p^r (\partial_i p^s)] \\ &= (\partial_i a_{rs}) p^r p^s + p_r (\partial_i p^r) + p_s (\partial_i p^s) \\ &= (\partial_i a_{rs}) p^r p^s + 2 p_r (\partial_i p^r), \end{aligned} \quad (2.2.25)$$

and noting that if we take the differential of (2.2.14):

$$\begin{aligned} dp^r &= d(a^{rm}) p_m + a^{rm} dp_m \\ &= (p_m \partial_i a^{rm}) dq^i + a^{rm} dp_m, \end{aligned} \quad (2.2.26)$$

we see that

$$\partial_i p^r = p_m (\partial_i a^{rm}), \quad (2.2.27)$$

which we substitute into (2.2.25) after changing the dummy index from m to s :

$$\partial_i (a_{rs} p^r p^s) = (\partial_i a_{rs}) p^r p^s + 2 p_r p_s (\partial_i a^{rs}). \quad (2.2.28)$$

We now write the second term on the RHS of (2.2.28) in contravariant form by first substituting for p_s :

$$2 p_r p_s (\partial_i a^{rs}) = 2 a_{ms} (\partial_i a^{rs}) p_r p^m. \quad (2.2.29)$$

Noticing that $a_{ms} a^{rs} = \delta_m^r$ allows us to write

$$\partial_i (a_{ms} a^{rs}) = (\partial_i a_{ms}) a^{rs} + a_{ms} (\partial_i a^{rs}) = 0,$$

and from the above

$$a_{ms} (\partial_i a^{rs}) = - a^{rs} (\partial_i a_{ms}), \quad (2.2.30)$$

so that for (2.2.29) we have

$$2 p_r p_s (\partial_i a^{rs}) = - 2 a^{rs} (\partial_i a_{ms}) p_r p^m. \quad (2.2.31)$$

Substituting for p_r in (2.2.31) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
2 p_r p_s (\partial_i a^{rs}) &= -2 a^{rs} a_{rn} (\partial_i a_{ms}) p^n p^m \\
&= -2 \delta_n^s (\partial_i a_{ms}) p^n p^m \\
&= -2 (\partial_i a_{mn}) p^n p^m .
\end{aligned} \tag{2.2.32}$$

Changing dummy indices and substituting back into (2.2.28) gives

$$\begin{aligned}
\partial_i (a_{rs} p^r p^s) &= (\partial_i a_{rs}) p^r p^s - 2 (\partial_i a_{rs}) p^r p^s \\
&= - (\partial_i a_{rs}) p^r p^s ,
\end{aligned} \tag{2.2.33}$$

which we substitute back into (2.2.24). Noticing that $\frac{da^{ii}}{dt} = (\partial_i a^{ii}) \dot{q}^i$ allows us to write

$$\dot{p}^i - (\partial_i a^{ii}) \dot{q}^i p_i - \frac{1}{2} a^{ii} (\partial_i a_{rs}) p^r p^s = - a^{ii} \partial_i V. \tag{2.2.34}$$

Writing $\dot{q}^k p_i$ in terms of the contravariant momenta and changing dummy indices for the last term on the LHS of (2.2.34) gives

$$\dot{p}^i - a_{ij} (\partial_i a^{ii}) p^j p^k - \frac{1}{2} a^{ii} (\partial_i a_{jk}) p^j p^k = - a^{ii} \partial_i V, \tag{2.2.35}$$

and after we substitute for $a_{ij} (\partial_i a^{ii})$, using the result from (2.2.30) we have

$$\dot{p}^i + a^{ii} (\partial_i a_{ij}) p^j p^k - \frac{1}{2} a^{ii} (\partial_i a_{jk}) p^j p^k = - a^{ii} \partial_i V. \tag{2.2.36}$$

Since the summation over the quadratic form $p^j p^k$ will give a symmetric result, we can perform the mixing operation (see p. 11) on the indices j and k to obtain for the middle term LHS:

$$\begin{aligned}
(\partial_k a_{ij}) p^j p^k &= (\partial_{(k} a_{|i|j)}) p^j p^k \\
&= \frac{1}{2} (\partial_k a_{ij} + \partial_j a_{ik}) p^j p^k .
\end{aligned} \tag{2.2.37}$$

Substituting back into (2.2.36) and rearranging gives the result

$$\dot{p}^i + \frac{1}{2} a^{ii} (\partial_k a_{ij} + \partial_j a_{ik} - \partial_i a_{jk}) p^j p^k = - a^{ii} \partial_i V. \tag{2.2.38}$$

Remembering the definition for the Christoffel symbols of the second kind we can write (2.2.38) more compactly as

$$\dot{p}^i + \Gamma^i_{jk} p^j p^k = - a^{ii} \partial_i V. \quad (2.2.39)$$

Recalling (2.1.35), we see that if the Hamiltonian variables q^i and p_i are both required to transform contravariantly, the resulting form of Hamilton's equations (2.2.22), is equivalent to a Lagrangian description of mechanics. The equivalence of (2.1.35) and (2.2.39) is easily established if we substitute for \ddot{q}^i and \dot{q}^i in (3.1.35), the contravariant momenta \dot{p}^i and p^i obtained from

$$\begin{aligned} p_i &= a_{ij} \dot{q}^j \\ a^{ii} p_i &= a^{ii} a_{ij} \dot{q}^j \\ p^i &= \delta^i_j \dot{q}^j = \dot{q}^i \\ \dot{p}^i &= \ddot{q}^i, \end{aligned} \quad (2.2.40)$$

where we have started from the relation given in (2.2.11).

3 Using Canonical Transformation Theory To Analyze Numerical Methods for Hamiltonian Systems

A fundamental assumption in physics is that if the mathematical representation of a physical law is changed by using another coordinate system, the physical content in the new coordinate system must remain the same. The advantage gained from a tensor formulation is that the mathematical description of the laws of nature no longer depends on a particular coordinate system. In physics, such formulations are termed *covariant* meaning "tensor form".

Hamiltonian dynamics proceeds by analogy with the above by requiring Hamilton's equations to remain *invariant in form* under a *transformation in phase space*. The class of transformations obeying this restriction are known as *canonical** transformations and are to be distinguished from tensor transformations which involve only coordinates. Although a transformation in phase space is not (in general) a tensor transformation, we can still use the compact tensor notation to formulate the principles by observing the contravariant and covariant transformation laws of q^i and p_i respectively.

In Section 3.1 we derive the familiar Poisson Bracket conditions [27] for canonical transformations using the tensor notation by considering a general transformation in phase space. In Section 3.2 we introduce the concept of an infinitesimal transformation and outline a procedure for the classification of a numerical integration method as canonical or non-canonical. We continue in Section 3.3 by providing a brief discussion of the *local truncation error* for a numerical integration method and then show how it can be used to classify non-canonical integration schemes. Section 3.4 then proceeds with the program of Sections 3.1, 3.2, and 3.3 to analyze Runge-Kutta numerical methods as applied to Hamiltonian systems with a single degree of freedom in coordinate space.

* Interestingly, the term *canonical* meaning "perfect" or "symmetrical" is derived from religious terminology referring to church law. Although its initial usage is unknown, one can speculate that it was used to label a certain aesthetic quality in algebraic forms.

3.1 Canonical Transformations

As noted in the previous section, a central point to a Hamiltonian formulation is the study of simultaneous transformations of the independent *coordinates* and *momenta*, q^i and p_i , to a new set Q^j and P_j , having the transformation equations:

$$\begin{aligned} Q^j &= Q^j(q^i, p_i) \\ P_j &= P_j(q^i, p_i), \end{aligned} \tag{3.1.1}$$

that we assume can be inverted. Eqs. (3.1.1) define a transformation in phase space and are to be distinguished from $Q^j = Q^j(q^i)$, defining a transformation of coordinates in the Riemannian manifold V_N , as discussed in Section 2.1. In Hamiltonian mechanics the only transformations that are of interest are transformations in which Hamilton's equations remain invariant in form. That is, we require that

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{Q}^j &= \frac{\partial H'}{\partial P_j} \\ \dot{P}_j &= -\frac{\partial H'}{\partial Q^j}, \end{aligned} \tag{3.1.2}$$

where $H' = H'(Q^j, P_j)$. The distinction between $H(q^i, p_i)$ and $H'(Q^j, P_j)$ is that although $T + V = E = T' + V'$, is a scalar invariant (the total energy must remain constant for any transformation), the functional form of H' may differ from that of H . With this in mind we write

$$H'(Q^j, P_j) = H(q^i, p_i), \tag{3.1.3}$$

and define the class of transformations having the functional form of (3.1.1) resulting in (3.1.2) as *canonical transformations*. Now that we have defined the necessary condition for a canonical transformation, we can continue by investigating the restrictions on such transformations.

To begin, consider the differentials of (3.1.1):

$$\begin{aligned}
dQ^j &= \frac{\partial Q^j}{\partial q^i} dq^i + \frac{\partial Q^j}{\partial p_i} dp_i \\
dP_j &= \frac{\partial P_j}{\partial q^i} dq^i + \frac{\partial P_j}{\partial p_i} dp_i .
\end{aligned} \tag{3.1.4}$$

Differentiating (3.1.1) with respect to t gives

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{Q}^j &= \frac{\partial Q^j}{\partial q^i} \dot{q}^i + \frac{\partial Q^j}{\partial p_i} \dot{p}_i \\
\dot{P}_j &= \frac{\partial P_j}{\partial q^i} \dot{q}^i + \frac{\partial P_j}{\partial p_i} \dot{p}_i ,
\end{aligned} \tag{3.1.5}$$

and from (3.1.3) we have

$$dH' = \frac{\partial H'}{\partial Q^k} dQ^k + \frac{\partial H'}{\partial P_k} dP_k . \tag{3.1.6}$$

Substituting for dQ^k and dP_k from (3.1.4) and collecting terms gives

$$dH' = \left(\frac{\partial Q^k}{\partial q^i} \frac{\partial H'}{\partial Q^k} + \frac{\partial P_k}{\partial q^i} \frac{\partial H'}{\partial P_k} \right) dq^i + \left(\frac{\partial Q^k}{\partial p_i} \frac{\partial H'}{\partial Q^k} + \frac{\partial P_k}{\partial p_i} \frac{\partial H'}{\partial P_k} \right) dp_i , \tag{3.1.7}$$

which we use to write

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{q}^i &= \frac{\partial H'}{\partial p_i} = \frac{\partial Q^k}{\partial p_i} \frac{\partial H'}{\partial Q^k} + \frac{\partial P_k}{\partial p_i} \frac{\partial H'}{\partial P_k} \\
\dot{p}_i &= -\frac{\partial H'}{\partial q^i} = -\frac{\partial Q^k}{\partial q^i} \frac{\partial H'}{\partial Q^k} - \frac{\partial P_k}{\partial q^i} \frac{\partial H'}{\partial P_k} .
\end{aligned} \tag{3.1.8}$$

Substituting (3.1.8) into (3.1.5) and then canceling terms gives the result

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{Q}^j &= \left(\frac{\partial Q^j}{\partial q^i} \frac{\partial P_k}{\partial p_i} - \frac{\partial P_k}{\partial q^i} \frac{\partial Q^j}{\partial p_i} \right) \frac{\partial H'}{\partial P_k} \\
\dot{P}_j &= -\left(\frac{\partial Q^k}{\partial q^i} \frac{\partial P_j}{\partial p_i} - \frac{\partial P_j}{\partial q^i} \frac{\partial Q^k}{\partial p_i} \right) \frac{\partial H'}{\partial Q^k} .
\end{aligned} \tag{3.1.9}$$

Comparing (3.1.9) with (3.1.2) we see that if the transformation is canonical, we must have

$$\frac{\partial Q^j}{\partial q^i} \frac{\partial P_k}{\partial p_i} - \frac{\partial P_k}{\partial q^i} \frac{\partial Q^j}{\partial p_i} = \delta_k^j, \quad (3.1.10)$$

which we recognize as the *Poisson Bracket* of the transformation. In the notation of the Poisson Bracket we write (3.1.10) as

$$[Q^j, P_k]_{PB} = \delta_k^j. \quad (3.1.11)$$

In Section 2.2 we noted that a symplectic formulation of Hamiltonian mechanics (p. 15) combines \dot{q}^i and \dot{p}_i into a single multiplet quantity $\dot{\xi}^i$. The usual procedure [12] is to then consider transformations in phase space which leave the Jacobian matrix of the transformation (commonly known as the *symplectic matrix*) invariant. The resulting requirements on the transformation matrix similarly lead to (3.1.10) but we see by inspection of (3.1.9) that (3.1.10) is obtained from either of Hamilton's equations separately without having to consider a single *multiplet* quantity combining \dot{q}^i and \dot{p}_i .

3.2 Infinitesimal Transformations

We note that in the previous section t was not included as a parameter in the transformation (3.1.1). The reason is that for our restricted treatment of conservative systems, we do not need to consider time as an explicit parameter. We do however need to consider transformations of the type:

$$\begin{aligned} q^i(t_o) &\rightarrow q^i(t_o + dt) \\ p_i(t_o) &\rightarrow p_i(t_o + dt), \end{aligned} \quad (3.2.1)$$

where dt can be taken to be some infinitesimal parameter ϵ . The transformation in (3.2.1) is known as an *infinitesimal transformation* [28] and provides the basis for analyzing numerical integration algorithms as transformations in phase space. An important characteristic of the transformation in (3.2.1) is that it

can be expressed in the form of (3.1.1) by considering the new variables as differing from the old by an infinitesimal amount. The transformation equations can then be written as

$$\begin{aligned} Q^j &= \delta_l^j (q^l + dq^l) \\ P_k &= \delta_k^l (p_l + dp_l), \end{aligned} \quad (3.2.2)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} dq^l &= \frac{\partial H}{\partial p_l} dt = \frac{\partial H(q^i, p_i)}{\partial p_l} \varepsilon = \dot{q}^l \varepsilon \\ dp_l &= -\frac{\partial H}{\partial q^l} dt = -\frac{\partial H(q^i, p_i)}{\partial q^l} \varepsilon = \dot{p}_l \varepsilon. \end{aligned} \quad (3.2.3)$$

The form of (3.1.1) is apparent if we substitute (3.2.3) into (3.2.2) and include the explicit dependence of \dot{q}^l and \dot{p}_l :

$$\begin{aligned} Q^j &= \delta_l^j (q^l + \dot{q}^l(q^i, p_i) \varepsilon) = Q^j(q^i, p_i) \\ P_k &= \delta_k^l (p_l + \dot{p}_l(q^i, p_i) \varepsilon) = P_k(q^i, p_i). \end{aligned} \quad (3.2.4)$$

We will find later that it is useful to consider a functional dependence on the infinitesimal parameter ε as well, without confusing this with any explicit dependence on t . We then write

$$\begin{aligned} Q^j &= Q^j(q^i, p_i, \varepsilon) \\ P_k &= P_k(q^i, p_i, \varepsilon). \end{aligned} \quad (3.2.5)$$

Now that we have a particular transformation in mind, we can use (3.1.10) to test if the transformation is canonical. Calculating the derivatives in (3.1.10) from (3.2.4) we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial Q^j}{\partial q^i} &= \delta_i^j (\delta_i^i + \frac{\partial \dot{q}^i}{\partial q^i} \varepsilon) = \delta_i^j + \frac{\partial \dot{q}^j}{\partial q^i} \varepsilon \\
\frac{\partial P_k}{\partial p_i} &= \delta_k^i (\delta_i^i + \frac{\partial \dot{p}_i}{\partial p_i} \varepsilon) = \delta_k^i + \frac{\partial \dot{p}_k}{\partial p_i} \varepsilon \\
\frac{\partial P_k}{\partial q^i} &= \delta_k^i \frac{\partial \dot{p}_i}{\partial q^i} \varepsilon = \frac{\partial \dot{p}_k}{\partial q^i} \varepsilon \\
\frac{\partial Q^j}{\partial p_i} &= \delta_i^j \frac{\partial \dot{q}^i}{\partial p_i} \varepsilon = \frac{\partial \dot{q}^j}{\partial p_i} \varepsilon,
\end{aligned} \tag{3.2.6}$$

and then combining these to form the Poisson Bracket and expanding gives the result

$$\begin{aligned}
[Q^j, P_k]_{PB} &= \delta_i^j \delta_k^i + \left(\frac{\partial \dot{p}_k}{\partial p_j} + \frac{\partial \dot{q}^j}{\partial q^k} \right) \varepsilon + \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}^j}{\partial q^i} \frac{\partial \dot{p}_k}{\partial p_i} - \frac{\partial \dot{p}_k}{\partial q^i} \frac{\partial \dot{q}^j}{\partial p_i} \right) \varepsilon^2 \\
&= \delta_k^j + \left(-\frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial p_j \partial q^k} + \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q^k \partial p_j} \right) \varepsilon + [\dot{q}^j, \dot{p}_k]_{PB} \varepsilon^2 \\
&= \delta_k^j + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2),
\end{aligned} \tag{3.2.7}$$

where we have substituted from Hamilton's equations for \dot{q}^j and \dot{p}_k in the second term on the RHS.

Referring to (2.2.12), we can check for conservation of energy by performing a series expansion of $H'(Q^j(\varepsilon), P_k(\varepsilon))$ in ε and then compare the result with (3.1.3). Expanding $H'(Q^j, P_j)$ about $\varepsilon = 0$, gives

$$\begin{aligned}
H'(Q^j, P_j) &= H'(Q^j, P_j) \Big|_{\varepsilon=0} + \left(\frac{\partial Q^j}{\partial \varepsilon} \frac{\partial H'}{\partial Q^j} + \frac{\partial P_j}{\partial \varepsilon} \frac{\partial H'}{\partial P_j} \right) \Big|_{\varepsilon=0} \varepsilon + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2) \\
&= H + \varepsilon \left(\dot{q} \frac{\partial}{\partial q} + \dot{p} \frac{\partial}{\partial p} \right) H + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \left(\dot{q} \frac{\partial}{\partial q} + \dot{p} \frac{\partial}{\partial p} \right)^2 H + \dots + \frac{\varepsilon^n}{n!} \left(\dot{q} \frac{\partial}{\partial q} + \dot{p} \frac{\partial}{\partial p} \right)^n H \\
&= H + \varepsilon (\dot{q}\dot{p} - \dot{p}\dot{q}) + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \left(\dot{q} \frac{\partial}{\partial q} + \dot{p} \frac{\partial}{\partial p} \right)^2 H + \dots + \frac{\varepsilon^n}{n!} \left(\dot{q} \frac{\partial}{\partial q} + \dot{p} \frac{\partial}{\partial p} \right)^n H \\
&= (1 + \varepsilon^2 \hat{H}^2 + \dots + \varepsilon^n \hat{H}^n) H = (e^{\varepsilon \hat{H}} - \varepsilon \hat{H}) H,
\end{aligned} \tag{3.2.8}$$

where we have used $\hat{H} = \left(\dot{q} \frac{\partial}{\partial q} + \dot{p} \frac{\partial}{\partial p} \right)$. Comparing (3.2.7) and (3.2.8) with (3.1.10) and (3.1.3),

we see that the transformation is both canonical and conserves energy to the same order in ε . Considering (3.2.7), and if we neglect terms higher than first order, the transformation is canonical and justifies in common terminology an *infinitesimal canonical transformation*. In the terminology of numerical analysis however, the above transformation is required to be *exactly* [13] canonical (all higher order terms must vanish) before it can be classified as a symplectic method.

The procedure outlined above using the Poisson Bracket of the transformation and a series expansion of H' will provide the primary means for investigating the Runge Kutta methods in Section 3.4. In the next section we discuss the local truncation error for a numerical integration scheme and then illustrate how it can be used to classify non-canonical integration methods.

3.3 Taylor Methods

In the language of numerical analysis, the transformation in (3.2.4) is known as the first order *Euler* [29], but is classified more generally as a Taylor method [30] of order one. Knowing the values for the first derivatives at $t = t_o$ allows us to extrapolate the values of q^i and p_i to the next time step, $t' = t_o + \varepsilon$. Using the new values for q^i and p_i we can repeat the process until we have reached some final time $t'_m = t_o + m\varepsilon$, where m is an integer denoting the total number of time steps taken. The Euler method is derived from a Taylor series expansion of (3.2.1), and so for purposes of illustration consider $q^i(t_o + \varepsilon) = q^i(t'(\varepsilon))$, which we expand about $t = t_o$ to get

$$\begin{aligned} q^i(t_o + \varepsilon) &= q^i(t_o) + \varepsilon \left(\frac{dt'}{d\varepsilon} \frac{dq(t')}{dt'} \right) \Big|_{\varepsilon=0} \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon^2 \left[\left(\frac{dt'}{d\varepsilon} \right)^2 \frac{d^2q(t')}{dt'^2} + \frac{d^2t'}{d\varepsilon^2} \frac{dq(t')}{dt'} \right] \Big|_{\varepsilon=0} + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) \\ &= q^i(t_o) + \varepsilon \dot{q}^i(t_o) + \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon^2 \ddot{q}^i(t_o) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) \end{aligned} \quad (3.3.1)$$

and if we truncate terms higher than first order we get the first order Euler approximation.

An important concept used to classify a numerical method is the local truncation error [19]. The local truncation error, $\tau(\varepsilon)$, at a specified step measures the amount by which the exact solution to the differential equation fails to satisfy the difference equation being used for the approximation. As an example, consider the first of Hamilton's equations (for the moment suppressing the index notation) as the initial value problem:

$$\dot{q} = f(q, p), \quad t_o \leq t \leq t_n, \quad q(t_o) = q_o. \quad (3.3.2)$$

Assume that there exists some number ξ in the interval $[t_o, t']$, such that

$$q(t_o + \varepsilon) = q(t_o) + \varepsilon \dot{q}(t_o) + \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon^2 \ddot{q}(\xi). \quad (3.3.3)$$

From (3.3.2) the exact value for $f(q, p)$ at $t = t_o$ is

$$\dot{q}(t_o) = f(q_o, p_o) \quad (3.3.4)$$

By definition [19] we write the local truncation error as the difference between $q(t_o + \varepsilon) - q(t_o)$ and $(t_o - t') f(q_o, p_o)$. Using (3.3.3) and (3.3.4) we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tau(\varepsilon) &= [q(t_o + \varepsilon) - q(t_o)] - (t' - t_o) f(q_o, p_o) \\
 &= \varepsilon \dot{q}(t_o) + \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon^2 \ddot{q}(\xi) - \varepsilon f(q_o, p_o) \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon^2 \ddot{q}(\xi),
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.3.5}$$

and when $\ddot{q}(\xi)$ is known to be bounded by some constant M , on the interval $[t_o, t']$, we write

$$|\tau(\varepsilon)| \leq \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} M. \tag{3.3.6}$$

The difference between the actual and approximated values is therefore, $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2)$. In our trivial example, it seems obvious that the accuracy of the approximation given in (3.3.1) will only be as good as the last term kept in the Taylor expansion. We find however that in other more complicated numerical integration schemes, the accuracy of the method can be established more rigorously proceeding as in (3.3.5).

Considering the results from Section 3.2, we see that the Euler method is non-symplectic and conserves energy to the same order as its local truncation error. For a second order Taylor method we write the transformation equations in (3.2.2) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q^j &= \delta_j^i (q^i + \varepsilon \dot{q}^i + \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon^2 \ddot{q}^i) \\
 P_k &= \delta_k^l (p_l + \varepsilon \dot{p}_l + \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon^2 \ddot{p}_l).
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.3.7}$$

Calculating derivatives from the above we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial Q^j}{\partial q^i} &= \delta_i^j + \varepsilon \frac{\partial \dot{q}^j}{\partial q^i} + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \frac{\partial \ddot{q}^j}{\partial q^i} \\
\frac{\partial P_k}{\partial p_i} &= \delta_k^i + \varepsilon \frac{\partial \dot{p}_k}{\partial p_i} + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \frac{\partial \ddot{p}_k}{\partial p_i} \\
\frac{\partial P_k}{\partial q^i} &= \varepsilon \frac{\partial \dot{p}_k}{\partial q^i} + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \frac{\partial \ddot{p}_k}{\partial p_i} \\
\frac{\partial Q^j}{\partial p_i} &= \varepsilon \frac{\partial \dot{q}^j}{\partial p_i} + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \frac{\partial \ddot{p}_k}{\partial q^i},
\end{aligned} \tag{3.3.8}$$

and then combining to form the Poisson Bracket gives the second order term

$$\frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \ddot{q}^j}{\partial q^k} + \frac{\partial \ddot{p}_k}{\partial p_j} + 2 [\dot{q}^j, \dot{p}_k]_{PB} \right), \tag{3.3.9}$$

where

$$[\dot{q}^j, \dot{p}_k]_{PB} = \left(-\frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q^i \partial p_j} \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial p_i \partial q^k} + \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q^i \partial q^k} \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial p_i \partial p_j} \right), \tag{3.3.10}$$

is non-zero, in general, for either of the Hamiltonians with the functional form:

$$\begin{aligned}
H(q^i, p_i) &= T(p_i) + V(q^i) \\
H(q^i, p_i) &= T(q^i, p_i) + V(q^i).
\end{aligned} \tag{3.3.11}$$

Performing a series expansion of $H'(Q^j(\varepsilon), P_k(\varepsilon))$ gives the second order term

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{1}{2} \frac{d^2 H'}{d\varepsilon^2} \Big|_{\varepsilon=0} &= \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \left[\left(\frac{\partial Q^j}{\partial \varepsilon} \right)^2 \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial Q^{j^2}} + \frac{\partial H'}{\partial Q^j} \frac{\partial^2 Q^j}{\partial \varepsilon^2} + \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial P_k \partial Q^j} \frac{\partial Q^j}{\partial \varepsilon} \frac{\partial P_k}{\partial \varepsilon} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \left(\frac{\partial P_k}{\partial \varepsilon} \right)^2 \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial P_k^2} + \frac{\partial H'}{\partial P_k} \frac{\partial^2 P_k}{\partial \varepsilon^2} + \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial P_k \partial Q^j} \frac{\partial Q^j}{\partial \varepsilon} \frac{\partial P_k}{\partial \varepsilon} \right] \Big|_{\varepsilon=0}
\end{aligned} \tag{3.3.12}$$

which simplifies to

$$\left. \frac{1}{2} \frac{d^2 H'}{d\varepsilon^2} \right|_{\varepsilon=0} = \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q^j \partial q^j} (\dot{q}^j)^2 + \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial p_k \partial p_k} (\dot{p}_k)^2 + \dot{q}^k \ddot{p}_k - \dot{p}_j \ddot{q}^j + \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial p_k \partial q^j} \dot{q}^j \dot{p}_k \right), \quad (3.3.13)$$

and is again non-zero. From the results in (3.3.9) and (3.3.13) we see that the second order Taylor method is non-symplectic and conserves energy to one order less than its local truncation error.

3.4 Second Order Runge-Kutta Methods

The Taylor methods outlined in the previous section have the advantage of high order local truncation error, but the disadvantage (besides being non-symplectic) of requiring the computation of higher order derivatives. For most problems this is a difficult or time-consuming procedure so in practice, the higher order Taylor methods are seldom used. The Euler method is usually unstable [31] and is therefore only used to illustrate the concepts behind other more complicated integration schemes.

Runge-Kutta methods on the other hand, have the high order local truncation error of the Taylor methods but do not require derivatives higher than first order. To approximate a solution over an interval, the methods combine information from several Euler-style steps and then use the information to match a Taylor series expansion up to some higher order. The details for specific Runge-Kutta derivations are given elsewhere [19] and so will not be reproduced here since our primary concern is only in the canonical nature of the algorithms.

In the following sections we first give the specific Runge-Kutta approximation and then, using the Poisson Bracket and H' expansion, we check for agreement with (3.1.10) and (3.1.3) respectively. Since the Runge-Kutta methods are constructed using a nesting of functions we will find it necessary to use a symbolic manipulation program to calculate the necessary derivatives. In particular, the *Mathematica* [32] computer software was used to check (and in some cases generate) results since

experience has shown that it is impossible for a single person to accurately perform the chain rule calculations by hand, which result in some cases with polynomials in excess of several hundred terms. Unfortunately, several intermediate calculations cannot be shown (due to memory limitations and output size), but appendices are given containing documented *Mathematica* input and output for the calculations described in the text. Appendix B contains the complete *Mathematica* session used for the *Modified Euler* method. Due to the similar nature of the calculations involved with the Modified Euler method, Appendices C and D will only contain *Mathematica* input and selected output used in the calculations for *Heun's* and the *Midpoint* method.

For simplicity in notation and analysis, the remaining part of this study will be limited to systems containing only a single degree of freedom in coordinate space. The tensor notation will not be used since it has no real purpose except to generalize (see (3.3.11) and (3.3.13)) the results to systems containing more than a single degree of freedom.

Modified Euler Method

In this section we analyze a second order Runge-Kutta method known as the *Modified Euler*, having a local truncation error of $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^3)$ [33]. At $t = t_o$ we will adopt the following convention: q and p corresponds to $q(t_o)$ and $p(t_o)$ respectively and so initially

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{q} &= \frac{\partial H(q,p)}{\partial p} \\ \dot{p} &= -\frac{\partial H(q,p)}{\partial q} . \end{aligned} \tag{3.4.1}$$

Runge-Kutta methods typically require successive stages of sub-transformations to build up a final approximation. The second order methods require only a single intermediate step and so for the first stage we will use the primed notation: $q' \equiv$ 1st stage, etc. while Q and P will designate the final transformation:

$$\begin{aligned} q &\rightarrow q(t_o + \varepsilon) \equiv Q(\varepsilon) \\ p &\rightarrow p(t_o + \varepsilon) \equiv P(\varepsilon). \end{aligned} \quad (3.4.2)$$

To begin we give the difference equation form of the Modified Euler method as taken from *Burden and Faires* [30]:

$$W = w + \frac{\varepsilon}{2} [f(w) + f(w + \varepsilon f(w))], \quad (3.4.3)$$

where W is defined to be an approximation to the initial value problem:

$$\dot{y} = f(t, y), \quad y(t_o) = w. \quad (3.4.4)$$

Translating the above difference equation to our Hamiltonian system of two simultaneous equations and using the previously defined notation we have:

$$\begin{aligned} Q &= q + \frac{\varepsilon}{2} [\dot{q}(q, p) + \dot{q}'(q + \varepsilon \dot{q}, p + \varepsilon \dot{p})] \\ P &= p + \frac{\varepsilon}{2} [\dot{p}(q, p) + \dot{p}'(q + \varepsilon \dot{q}, p + \varepsilon \dot{p})], \end{aligned} \quad (3.4.5)$$

which advances the state of the system for one time step from $t = t_o$ to $t = t_o + \varepsilon$. Using the primed notation we write the transformation in (3.4.5) as

$$\begin{aligned} Q &= q + \frac{\varepsilon}{2} [\dot{q} + \dot{q}'(q', p')] \\ P &= p + \frac{\varepsilon}{2} [\dot{p} + \dot{p}'(q', p')], \end{aligned} \quad (3.4.6)$$

where we have defined $q' = q + \varepsilon \dot{q}$ and $p' = p + \varepsilon \dot{p}$. From Section 3.2 we recognize the first stage of the transformation as the first order Euler method and after substituting the results from (3.2.7) into (3.1.9), we find that Hamilton's equations for the first stage are

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{q}' &= \frac{\partial H(q', p')}{\partial p'} + \varepsilon^2 [\dot{q}, \dot{p}]_{PB} \frac{\partial H(q', p')}{\partial p'} \\ \dot{p}' &= -\frac{\partial H(q', p')}{\partial q'} - \varepsilon^2 [\dot{q}, \dot{p}]_{PB} \frac{\partial H(q', p')}{\partial q'}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.4.7)$$

Calculating derivatives of Q and P from (3.4.6):

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial Q}{\partial q} &= 1 + \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial q} + \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial q'} \right) + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial q} \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial q'} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial q} \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial p'} \right) \\
\frac{\partial P}{\partial p} &= 1 + \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial p} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial p'} \right) + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial p'} + \frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial q'} \right) \\
\frac{\partial P}{\partial q} &= \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial p} + \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial p'} \right) + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial q'} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial p'} \right) \\
\frac{\partial Q}{\partial p} &= \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial q} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial q'} \right) + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial q} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial p'} + \frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial q} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial q'} \right),
\end{aligned} \tag{3.4.8}$$

and then combining to form the Poisson Bracket gives

$$\begin{aligned}
[Q, P]_{PB} &= 1 + \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial q} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial p} + \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial q'} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial p'} \right) \\
&\quad + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \left[[\dot{q}, \dot{p}]_{PB} + [\dot{q}', \dot{p}']_{PB} \right. \\
&\quad \quad \left. + \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial q'} \frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial q} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial p'} \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial p} + \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial p'} \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial q} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial q'} \frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial p} \right] \\
&\quad + \frac{\varepsilon^3}{4} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial q'} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial p'} \right) [\dot{q}, \dot{p}]_{PB} \\
&\quad + \frac{\varepsilon^4}{4} [\dot{q}, \dot{p}]_{PB} [\dot{q}', \dot{p}']_{PB} .
\end{aligned} \tag{3.4.9}$$

Substituting (3.4.1) and (3.4.7) into (3.4.9) we see that the odd order terms cancel and we are left with

$$\begin{aligned}
[Q, P]_{PB} &= 1 + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \left\{ [\dot{q}, \dot{p}]_{PB} + [\dot{q}', \dot{p}']_{PB} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial q'} \frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial q} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial p'} \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial p} + \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial p'} \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial q} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial q'} \frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial p} \right\} \\
&\quad + \frac{\varepsilon^4}{4} [\dot{q}, \dot{p}]_{PB} [\dot{q}', \dot{p}']_{PB} + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^6) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^8),
\end{aligned} \tag{3.4.10}$$

and after expanding the Poisson Brackets in the above and again substituting from (3.4.1) and (3.4.7) we get

$$\begin{aligned}
[Q, P]_{PB} = & 1 + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \left[\left(\frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q^2} - \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial q'^2} \right) \left(\frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q^2} - \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial q'^2} \right) - \left(\frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q \partial p} - \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial q' \partial p'} \right)^2 \right] \\
& + \frac{\varepsilon^4}{4} \left\{ \left[\frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q^2} \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial p^2} - \left(\frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q \partial p} \right)^2 \right] \left[2 \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q \partial p} \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial q' \partial p'} - 3 \left(\frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial q' \partial p'} \right)^2 \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. - \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q^2} \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial p'^2} - \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial p^2} \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial q'^2} + 3 \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial q'^2} \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial p'^2} \right] \right\} + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^5),
\end{aligned} \tag{3.4.11}$$

where we have used $H' = H'(q', p')$. Performing a series expansion for the derivatives in (3.4.11) involving $H'(q', p')$, the first two terms in each case are

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^2 H'(q', p')}{\partial q' \partial p'} &= \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q \partial p} + \varepsilon \left(\dot{q} \frac{\partial^3 H}{\partial q^2 \partial p} + \dot{p} \frac{\partial^3 H}{\partial q \partial p^2} \right) \\
&\quad + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \left(\dot{q}^2 \frac{\partial^4 H}{\partial q^3 \partial p} + \dot{p}^2 \frac{\partial^4 H}{\partial q \partial p^3} + \dot{q} \dot{p} \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q^2 \partial p^2} \right) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) \\
\frac{\partial^2 H'(q', p')}{\partial q'^2} &= \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q^2} + \varepsilon \left(\dot{q} \frac{\partial^3 H}{\partial q^3} + \dot{p} \frac{\partial^3 H}{\partial q^2 \partial p} \right) \\
&\quad + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \left(\dot{q}^2 \frac{\partial^4 H}{\partial q^4} + \dot{p}^2 \frac{\partial^4 H}{\partial q^2 \partial p^2} + \dot{q} \dot{p} \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q^3 \partial p} \right) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) \\
\frac{\partial^2 H'(q', p')}{\partial p'^2} &= \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial p^2} + \varepsilon \left(\dot{q} \frac{\partial^3 H}{\partial q \partial p^2} + \dot{p} \frac{\partial^3 H}{\partial p^3} \right) \\
&\quad + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \left(\dot{q}^2 \frac{\partial^4 H}{\partial q^2 \partial p^2} + \dot{p}^2 \frac{\partial^4 H}{\partial p^4} + \dot{q} \dot{p} \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q \partial p^3} \right) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3),
\end{aligned} \tag{3.4.12}$$

and after substituting (3.4.12) into (3.4.11) and simplifying we find that

$$\begin{aligned}
[Q, P]_{PB} = 1 + \frac{\varepsilon^4}{4} & \left\{ \left[\left(\frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q \partial p} \right)^2 - \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q^2} \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial p^2} \right]^2 - \left(\dot{q} \frac{\partial^3 H}{\partial q^2 \partial p} + \dot{p} \frac{\partial^3 H}{\partial q \partial p^2} \right)^2 \right. \\
& \left. + \left(\dot{q} \frac{\partial^3 H}{\partial q \partial p^2} + \dot{p} \frac{\partial^3 H}{\partial p^3} \right) \left(\dot{q} \frac{\partial^3 H}{\partial q^3} + \dot{p} \frac{\partial^3 H}{\partial q^2 \partial p} \right) \right\} + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^5), \tag{3.4.13}
\end{aligned}$$

showing that the method is non-symplectic to one order higher than its local truncation error.

To check energy conservation, we perform a series expansion of $H'(Q(\varepsilon), P(\varepsilon))$, where Q and P are given by (3.4.6). Writing out the first three terms:

$$\begin{aligned}
H'(Q, P) = H'(Q, P)|_{\varepsilon=0} + \varepsilon & \left(\frac{\partial Q}{\partial \varepsilon} \frac{\partial}{\partial Q} + \frac{\partial P}{\partial \varepsilon} \frac{\partial}{\partial P} \right) H' \Big|_{\varepsilon=0} \\
+ \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} & \left[\left(\frac{\partial Q}{\partial \varepsilon} \frac{\partial}{\partial Q} + \frac{\partial P}{\partial \varepsilon} \frac{\partial}{\partial P} \right)^2 + \frac{\partial}{\partial \varepsilon} \left(\frac{\partial Q}{\partial \varepsilon} \frac{\partial}{\partial Q} + \frac{\partial P}{\partial \varepsilon} \frac{\partial}{\partial P} \right) \right] H' \Big|_{\varepsilon=0} \\
+ \frac{\varepsilon^3}{3!} & \left[\left(\frac{\partial Q}{\partial \varepsilon} \frac{\partial}{\partial Q} + \frac{\partial P}{\partial \varepsilon} \frac{\partial}{\partial P} \right)^3 + \frac{\partial^3 Q}{\partial \varepsilon^3} \frac{\partial}{\partial Q} + \frac{\partial^3 P}{\partial \varepsilon^3} \frac{\partial}{\partial P} \right. \\
& + 3 \frac{\partial Q}{\partial \varepsilon} \frac{\partial^2 Q}{\partial \varepsilon^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial Q^2} + 3 \frac{\partial P}{\partial \varepsilon} \frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial \varepsilon^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial P^2} \\
& \left. + 3 \frac{\partial Q}{\partial \varepsilon} \frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial \varepsilon^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial Q \partial P} + 3 \frac{\partial P}{\partial \varepsilon} \frac{\partial^2 Q}{\partial \varepsilon^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial Q \partial P} \right] H' \Big|_{\varepsilon=0} + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^4), \tag{3.4.14}
\end{aligned}$$

and then substituting

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial Q}{\partial \varepsilon} \Big|_{\varepsilon=0} &= \dot{q} \\ \frac{\partial^2 Q}{\partial \varepsilon^2} \Big|_{\varepsilon=0} &= \dot{q} \dot{p} + \dot{q}^2 \\ \frac{\partial P}{\partial \varepsilon} \Big|_{\varepsilon=0} &= \dot{p} \\ \frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial \varepsilon^2} \Big|_{\varepsilon=0} &= \dot{q} \dot{p} + \dot{p}^2,\end{aligned}$$

(3.4.15)

obtained from (3.4.6), and then evaluating all other terms at $\varepsilon = 0$ we get

$$H'(Q, P) = \left[1 - \frac{\varepsilon^3}{12} \left(\dot{q} \frac{\partial}{\partial q} - \dot{p} \frac{\partial}{\partial p} \right)^3 \right] H(q, p) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^4), \quad (3.4.16)$$

showing that the Modified Euler method conserves energy to the same order as its local truncation error.

Heun's Method

The difference equation form of Heun's method [30] is

$$W = w + \frac{\varepsilon}{4} [f(w) + 3f(w + \frac{2}{3}\varepsilon f(w))], \quad (3.4.17)$$

where W is defined to be an approximation to the initial value problem in (3.4.4). For a Hamiltonian system with a single degree of freedom, (3.4.17) takes the form:

$$\begin{aligned}Q &= q + \frac{\varepsilon}{4} [\dot{q} + 3\dot{q}'(q', p')] \\ P &= p + \frac{\varepsilon}{4} [\dot{p} + 3\dot{p}'(q', p')],\end{aligned} \quad (3.4.18)$$

where $q' = q + \frac{2}{3}\varepsilon \dot{q}$ and $p' = p + \frac{2}{3}\varepsilon \dot{p}$ define the first stage of the transformation. After calculating the Poisson Bracket for the first stage we get analogous to (3.4.7):

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{q}' &= \frac{\partial H(q', p')}{\partial p'} + \frac{4}{9}\varepsilon^2 [\dot{q}, \dot{p}]_{PB} \frac{\partial H(q', p')}{\partial p'} \\ \dot{p}' &= -\frac{\partial H(q', p')}{\partial q'} - \frac{4}{9}\varepsilon^2 [\dot{q}, \dot{p}]_{PB} \frac{\partial H(q', p')}{\partial q'}.\end{aligned}\tag{3.4.19}$$

Calculating derivatives of Q and P from (3.4.18):

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial Q}{\partial q} &= 1 + \frac{\varepsilon}{4} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial q} + \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial q'} \right) + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial q} \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial q'} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial q} \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial p'} \right) \\ \frac{\partial P}{\partial p} &= 1 + \frac{\varepsilon}{4} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial p} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial p'} \right) + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial p'} + \frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial q'} \right) \\ \frac{\partial P}{\partial q} &= \frac{\varepsilon}{4} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial p} + \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial p'} \right) + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial q} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial q'} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial q} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial p'} \right) \\ \frac{\partial Q}{\partial p} &= \frac{\varepsilon}{4} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial q} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial q'} \right) + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial p'} + \frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial q'} \right),\end{aligned}\tag{3.4.20}$$

and then combining to form the Poisson Bracket gives

$$\begin{aligned}
[Q, P]_{PB} = & 1 + \frac{\epsilon}{4} \left[\frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial q} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial p} + 3 \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial q'} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial p'} \right) \right] \\
& + \frac{\epsilon^2}{16} \left[[\dot{q}, \dot{p}]_{PB} + 9 [\dot{q}', \dot{p}']_{PB} + 3 \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial q} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial p'} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial q'} \right) \right. \\
& \quad \left. + 5 \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial q'} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial q} \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial p'} \right) + 8 \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial q} \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial q'} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial p'} \right) \right] \\
& + \frac{\epsilon^3}{8} \left[\left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial q'} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial p'} \right) [\dot{q}, \dot{p}]_{PB} + 3 \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial q} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial p} \right) [\dot{q}', \dot{p}']_{PB} \right] \\
& + \frac{\epsilon^4}{4} [\dot{q}, \dot{p}]_{PB} [\dot{q}', \dot{p}']_{PB} .
\end{aligned} \tag{3.4.21}$$

Substituting (3.4.1) into (3.4.21):

$$\begin{aligned}
[Q, P]_{PB} = & 1 + \frac{3}{4} \epsilon \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial q'} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial p'} \right) \\
& + \frac{\epsilon^2}{16} \left[[\dot{q}, \dot{p}]_{PB} + 9 [\dot{q}', \dot{p}']_{PB} + 3 \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial q} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial p'} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial q'} \right) \right. \\
& \quad \left. + 5 \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial q'} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial q} \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial p'} \right) + 8 \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial q} \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial q'} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial p'} \right) \right] \\
& + \frac{\epsilon^3}{8} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial q'} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial p'} \right) [\dot{q}, \dot{p}]_{PB} \\
& + \frac{\epsilon^4}{4} [\dot{q}, \dot{p}]_{PB} [\dot{q}', \dot{p}']_{PB} ,
\end{aligned} \tag{3.4.22}$$

and then substituting (3.4.19) we see that the odd order terms cancel leaving

$$\begin{aligned}
[Q,P]_{PB} = & 1 + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{16} \left[[\dot{q}, \dot{p}]_{PB} + 9 [\dot{q}', \dot{p}']_{PB} + 3 \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial q} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial p'} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial q'} \right) \right. \\
& + 5 \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial q'} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial q} \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial p'} \right) + 8 \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial q} \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial q'} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial p'} \right) \left. \right] \quad (3.4.23) \\
& + \frac{\varepsilon^4}{4} [\dot{q}, \dot{p}]_{PB} [\dot{q}', \dot{p}']_{PB} .
\end{aligned}$$

Expanding the Poisson Brackets in the above and again substituting from (3.4.1) and (3.4.19) gives

$$\begin{aligned}
[Q,P]_{PB} = & 1 + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \left[\left(\frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q^2} - \frac{9}{5} \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial q'^2} \right) \left(\frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial p^2} - 5 \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial p'^2} \right) \right. \\
& - \left. \left(\frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q} \frac{\partial H}{\partial p} + \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial q'} \frac{\partial H'}{\partial p'} \right) \left(\frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q} \frac{\partial H}{\partial p} - 9 \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial q'} \frac{\partial H'}{\partial p'} \right) - \frac{16}{5} \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial p^2} \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial q'^2} \right] \\
& + \frac{\varepsilon^4}{4} \left\{ \left[\frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q^2} \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial p^2} - \left(\frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q} \frac{\partial H}{\partial p} \right)^2 \right] \left[10 \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q} \frac{\partial H}{\partial p} \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial q'} \frac{\partial H'}{\partial p'} - 27 \left(\frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial q'} \frac{\partial H'}{\partial p'} \right)^2 \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. - 5 \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q^2} \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial p'^2} - 5 \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial p^2} \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial q'^2} + 27 \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial q'^2} \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial p'^2} \right] \right\} + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^5), \quad (3.4.24)
\end{aligned}$$

and after substituting for the derivatives involving $H'(q', p')$ from (3.4.12) and simplifying we find that

$$\begin{aligned}
[Q,P]_{PB} = & 1 + \frac{\varepsilon^3}{4} \left[\dot{q} \left(\frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial p^2} \frac{\partial^3 H}{\partial q^3} + \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q^2} \frac{\partial^3 H}{\partial q \partial p^2} - 2 \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q} \frac{\partial^3 H}{\partial p \partial q^2 \partial p} \right) \right. \\
& + \dot{p} \left(\frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q^2} \frac{\partial^3 H}{\partial p^3} + \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial p^2} \frac{\partial^3 H}{\partial q^2 \partial p} - 2 \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q} \frac{\partial^3 H}{\partial p \partial q \partial p^2} \right) \left. \right] + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^4), \quad (3.4.25)
\end{aligned}$$

showing that Heun's method is non-symplectic to the same order as its local truncation error.

To check energy conservation we refer to (3.4.14) and then after taking derivatives of (3.4.18) we get the same result as in (3.4.15):

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial Q}{\partial \varepsilon} \Big|_{\varepsilon=0} &= \dot{q} \\ \frac{\partial^2 Q}{\partial \varepsilon^2} \Big|_{\varepsilon=0} &= \dot{q} \dot{p} + \dot{q}^2 \\ \frac{\partial P}{\partial \varepsilon} \Big|_{\varepsilon=0} &= \dot{p} \\ \frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial \varepsilon^2} \Big|_{\varepsilon=0} &= \dot{q} \dot{p} + \dot{p}^2,\end{aligned}$$

which we substitute into (3.4.14) and then after evaluating all other terms at $\varepsilon = 0$ we get

$$H'(Q, P) = H(q, p) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^4). \quad (3.4.26)$$

From the above result we conclude that Heun's method conserves energy to one order higher than its local truncation error.

Midpoint Method

The difference equation form of the Midpoint method [30] is

$$W = w + \varepsilon f(w + \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon f(w)), \quad (3.4.27)$$

where W is defined to be an approximation to the initial value problem in (3.4.4). Translating the above difference equation to our Hamiltonian system gives

$$\begin{aligned}Q &= q + \varepsilon \dot{q}(q', p') \\ P &= p + \varepsilon \dot{p}(q', p'),\end{aligned} \quad (3.4.28)$$

where $q' = q + \frac{\epsilon}{2} \dot{q}$ and $p' = p + \frac{\epsilon}{2} \dot{p}$ define the first stage of the transformation. The Poisson Bracket for the first stage is

$$\begin{aligned} [q', p'] &= 1 + \frac{\epsilon^2}{4} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial q} \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial p} - \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial q} \frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial p} \right) \\ &= 1 + \frac{\epsilon^2}{4} [\dot{q}, \dot{p}], \end{aligned} \quad (3.4.29)$$

which we substitute into (3.1.9) to get

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{q}' &= \frac{\partial H(q', p')}{\partial p'} + \frac{\epsilon^2}{4} [\dot{q}, \dot{p}]_{PB} \frac{\partial H(q', p')}{\partial p'} \\ \dot{p}' &= -\frac{\partial H(q', p')}{\partial q'} - \frac{\epsilon^2}{4} [\dot{q}, \dot{p}]_{PB} \frac{\partial H(q', p')}{\partial q'}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.4.30)$$

Calculating derivatives of Q and P from (3.4.28):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial Q}{\partial q} &= 1 + \epsilon \frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial q} + \frac{\epsilon^2}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial q} \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial q'} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial q} \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial p'} \right) \\ \frac{\partial P}{\partial p} &= 1 + \epsilon \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial p} + \frac{\epsilon^2}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial p'} + \frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial q'} \right) \\ \frac{\partial P}{\partial q} &= \epsilon \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial q} + \frac{\epsilon^2}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial q} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial q'} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial q} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial p'} \right) \\ \frac{\partial Q}{\partial p} &= \epsilon \frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial p} + \frac{\epsilon^2}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial p'} + \frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial q'} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (3.4.31)$$

and then combining to form the Poisson Bracket gives

$$\begin{aligned}
[Q, P]_{PB} &= 1 + \varepsilon \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial q'} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial p'} \right) \\
&+ \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial q} \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial q'} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial p'} + \frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial q'} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial q} \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial p'} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + 2 \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial q'} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial p'} + 2 \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial p'} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial q'} \right) \\
&+ \frac{\varepsilon^3}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial q} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial p} \right) [\dot{q}', \dot{p}']_{PB} \\
&+ \frac{\varepsilon^4}{4} [\dot{q}, \dot{p}]_{PB} [\dot{q}', \dot{p}']_{PB} .
\end{aligned}
\tag{3.4.32}$$

Substituting (3.4.1) and (3.4.30) into (3.4.32), we see that the odd order terms cancel and we are left with

$$\begin{aligned}
[Q, P]_{PB} &= 1 + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial q} \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial q'} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial p'} + \frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial q'} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial q} \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial p'} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + 2 \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial q'} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial p'} + 2 \frac{\partial \dot{q}'}{\partial p'} \frac{\partial \dot{p}'}{\partial q'} \right) \\
&+ \frac{\varepsilon^4}{4} [\dot{q}, \dot{p}]_{PB} [\dot{q}', \dot{p}']_{PB} + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^6) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^8) ,
\end{aligned}
\tag{3.4.33}$$

and after expanding the Poisson Brackets in the above and again substituting from (3.4.1) and (3.4.30) we get

$$\begin{aligned}
[Q,P]_{PB} = & 1 - \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \left[\left(\frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q \partial p} \right)^2 - \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q \partial p} \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial q' \partial p'} + \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q^2} \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial p'^2} \right. \\
& \left. + \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial p^2} \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial q'^2} - \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial q'^2} \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial p'^2} \right] \\
& + \frac{\varepsilon^4}{8} \left\{ \left[\frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q^2} \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial p^2} - \left(\frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q \partial p} \right)^2 \right] \left[2 \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q \partial p} \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial q' \partial p'} - 6 \left(\frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial q' \partial p'} \right)^2 \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. - \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q^2} \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial p'^2} - \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial p^2} \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial q'^2} + 6 \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial q'^2} \frac{\partial^2 H'}{\partial p'^2} \right] \right\} + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^5).
\end{aligned}
\tag{3.4.33}$$

Substituting for the derivatives involving $H'(q', p')$ from (3.4.12) and simplifying we find that

$$\begin{aligned}
[Q,P]_{PB} = & 1 + \frac{\varepsilon^3}{2} \left[\dot{q} \left(\frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial p^2} \frac{\partial^3 H}{\partial q^3} + \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q^2} \frac{\partial^3 H}{\partial q \partial p^2} - 2 \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q \partial p} \frac{\partial^3 H}{\partial q^2 \partial p} \right) \right. \\
& \left. + \dot{p} \left(\frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q^2} \frac{\partial^3 H}{\partial p^3} + \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial p^2} \frac{\partial^3 H}{\partial q^2 \partial p} - 2 \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial q \partial p} \frac{\partial^3 H}{\partial q \partial p^2} \right) \right] + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^4),
\end{aligned}
\tag{3.4.34}$$

showing that the Midpoint method is non-symplectic to the same order as its local truncation error.

To check energy conservation we refer to (3.4.14) and then after differentiating (3.4.28) with respect to ε , we get the same result as in (3.4.15). Substituting (3.4.15) into (3.4.14) and evaluating all other terms at $\varepsilon = 0$ gives

$$H'(Q, P) = \left[1 + \frac{\varepsilon^3}{24} \left(\dot{q} \frac{\partial}{\partial q} + \dot{p} \frac{\partial}{\partial p} \right)^3 \right] H(q, p) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^4), \tag{3.4.35}$$

and we see that the Midpoint method conserves energy to the same order as its local truncation error.

4 Results & Discussion

Interpreting the result from Section 2.2, we see that the fundamental distinction of Hamiltonian dynamics (from other formulations of mechanics) is that it requires both contravariant and covariant transformation laws for the variables q and p respectively. Combining both variables into a single vector quantity destroys the canonical form of Hamilton's equations and leads us back to Lagrangian dynamics. It should be noted however, that the result is only valid for Hamiltonian systems with a velocity independent potential (see (2.2.11)). From the definition of the conjugate momenta in (2.2.2) we may also interpret the contravariant and covariant transformation laws as providing the distinction between *conjugate* vector quantities. A brief note on the mathematical relation between conjugate variables can be found in [34].

In Section 3.4, three commonly used numerical integration algorithms were classified in terms of the infinitesimal time step parameter ϵ , based on their energy conservation and canonical transformation properties. We found that the Modified Euler method was non-symplectic to one order higher and conserved energy to the same order as its local truncation error. Heun's method on the other hand, was non-symplectic to the same order and conserved energy to one order higher than its local truncation error. Finally, the Midpoint method was both non-symplectic and conserved energy to the same order as its local truncation error. The results are summarized in Table 4.1.

Method	Non-Symplectic Effects	Energy Conservation
Modified Euler	$\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^4)$	$\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^3)$
Heun's	$\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^3)$	$\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^4)$
Midpoint	$\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^3)$	$\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^3)$

**Table 4.1. Results for Second Order Runge-Kutta Methods
with Local Truncation Error $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^3)$**

Considering the Modified Euler method, the non-symplectic properties of the algorithm are apparent if we substitute the Poisson Bracket (3.4.13) into (3.1.9), which we rewrite for convenience below

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{Q}^j &= [Q^j, P_k]_{PB} \frac{\partial H'}{\partial P_k} \\ \dot{P}_j &= -[Q^k, P_j]_{PB} \frac{\partial H'}{\partial Q^k}.\end{aligned}$$

Making the substitution we find that for a Hamiltonian system with a single degree of freedom

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{Q} &= \frac{\partial H'}{\partial P} + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^4) \\ \dot{P} &= -\frac{\partial H'}{\partial Q} + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^4),\end{aligned}$$

showing that the system loses its Hamiltonian character to at least one order higher than the numerical truncation error of the method. Substituting now for H' from (3.4.16) we see that the effects of numerical truncation error are contained in the result for conservation of energy and we then have

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{Q} &= \frac{\partial H}{\partial P} + \underbrace{\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3)}_{\text{Energy Conservation}} + \underbrace{\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^4)}_{\text{Non-Symplectic Effects}} \\ \dot{P} &= -\frac{\partial H}{\partial Q} + \underbrace{\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3)}_{\text{Energy Conservation}} + \underbrace{\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^4)}_{\text{Non-Symplectic Effects}}.\end{aligned}$$

From the above result, we conclude that the non-symplectic effects are unimportant when compared to the numerical truncation error of the method. For Heun's method we are led to a similar result but with the effects of energy conservation and the non-symplectic properties reversed. For the Midpoint method, both effects are present to the same order and so we have the expected result for all three of the explicit Runge-Kutta methods: the Hamiltonian structure is lost to the same order as the numerical truncation error.

Sanz-Serna [15] has reported that it is not possible, in general, to construct implicit Runge-Kutta algorithms that conserve both energy *and* the Hamiltonian structure exactly. The results from this work show that in such cases it would be useless to consider using a symplectic algorithm.

To summarize the symplectic algorithms we find that there are two general classes [10]:

- i) Algorithms based on the generating function approach from Hamilton-Jacobi theory.
- ii) Implicit algorithms.

Algorithms from the first class lead to methods that are reminiscent of the Taylor series approach discussed in Section 3.3 and have the disadvantage of requiring higher order derivatives of H . They also have only limited applicability since in order to solve the Hamilton-Jacobi equation and find a suitable generating function, one must first have a Hamiltonian of the form given at the top of p. 3. Several examples using this approach can be found in [11].

Algorithms from the second class suffer from two serious drawbacks when compared to explicit methods of the same order:

- 1) The methods are generally more complicated and difficult to implement.
- 2) The implicit approach requires the use of matrix methods which are generally slower and require additional memory [35].

From a practical standpoint, the additional time expense of coding an implicit Runge-Kutta method, as well as the reduced performance cost, may offset the advantages gained from using this type of algorithm.

The general approach used in Section 3.4 to test the second order Runge-Kutta methods could easily be extended to higher order methods. Preliminary calculations [36] on a general fourth order explicit Runge-Kutta scheme have already shown that energy is conserved to one order higher ($\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^6)$) than the local truncation error of the method ($\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^5)$). For the fourth order Runge-Kutta method, output line 27 in Appendix B gives 419 polynomial terms compared to 27 terms for the second order method. The size of the Poisson Bracket polynomials resulting from the chain-rule evaluations of the higher order Runge-Kutta methods, will however, limit the extent to which these calculations can be performed due to computer memory limitations.

Appendix A The Action Line Element

In Section 2.1 we considered the kinematic line element, giving a distance element in the manifold of configurations for a system with no external forces. If we consider the possibility of external forces we must solve (2.1.35) for the dynamical trajectory in configuration space. For a conservative system we had

$$(\ddot{q}^i + \Gamma^i_{jk} \dot{q}^j \dot{q}^k) = -a^{ii} \frac{\partial V}{\partial q^i}, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where V is the potential energy for the system. A standard derivation [23] (using a variational principle and the concept of *action*) shows that (A.1) can be written in the form of (2.1.27). We therefore conclude that the natural trajectories for a given energy constant $E = T + V$, are geodesics in the manifold of configurations when the action line element is taken. By analogy with (2.1.1) the action line element is given by

$$ds^2 = b_{ii} dq^i dq^i, \quad (\text{A.2})$$

and the Christoffel symbols in (2.1.24) and (2.1.26) are now defined from the new metric tensor b_{ii} . Following Synge and Schild [5] we can define the relation between the two metric tensors a_{ii} and b_{ii} to be

$$b_{ii} = 2(E - V) a_{ii} = 2T a_{ii}. \quad (\text{A.3})$$

From (2.1.24) and (2.1.26) the definition of the Christoffel symbols of the first and second kind in terms of the metric tensor a_{ii} is

$$[il, m]_a = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial a_{im}}{\partial q^l} + \frac{\partial a_{lm}}{\partial q^i} - \frac{\partial a_{ii}}{\partial q^m} \right) \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$$\Gamma^r_{il} = a^{rm} [il, m].$$

Substituting (A.3) into (A.4) we can establish the relation between the Christoffel symbols for each metric tensor (which we denote with sub-subscripts a and b) as

$$\Gamma_{a\ ii}^r = \frac{1}{2} \Gamma_{b\ ii}^r + \frac{1}{4(E-V)} \left(\delta_i^r \frac{\partial V}{\partial x^i} + \delta_i^r \frac{\partial V}{\partial x^i} - a_{ii} a^{rm} \frac{\partial V}{\partial x^i} \right), \quad (\text{A.5})$$

and we then write the geodesic equations for each metric:

$$(\ddot{q}^i + \Gamma_{jk}^i \dot{q}^j \dot{q}^k) = 0 \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$$(\ddot{q}^i + \Gamma_{jk}^i \dot{q}^j \dot{q}^k) = 0. \quad (\text{A.7})$$

In summary, the solutions to (A.6) are curves in configuration space describing what motion is physically possible for a given system under constraint equations (2.1.9). The kinematical line element given by (2.1.29) defines distance along these curves. Solutions to (A.7) determine a natural trajectory on the surface defined by the curves in (A.6) for a system under the influence of external forces. Distance along a natural trajectory is given by the action line element in (A.2).

Appendix B *Mathematica* Session: The Modified Euler Method

The *Mathematica* program uses a text based interface which allows it a certain degree of portability across a variety of hardware platforms. As a result, the output generated by the program can only mimic standard mathematical notation*. For convenience to the reader, the *Mathematica* notation is explained as it is encountered in the Appendix.

The actual *Mathematica* session** that was used for the calculations described in the text for the Modified Euler method is given below.

```
In[1]:=
Share [ ]
```

The `Share[]` command reduces the amount of memory required to store a given expression by not duplicating common sub-expressions throughout memory. The following variable names will be used in the *Mathematica* session to represent the notation used in the text:

$$q1 \equiv q',$$

$$p1 \equiv p',$$

$$qd \equiv \dot{q},$$

* Typeset quality results can however, be obtained from *Mathematica* output with the utility `TeXForm[]` but is only useful if an appropriate *TeX* compiler is available.

** For reference, the calculations were performed on a homebuilt 50 MHz i486 with 8 MB of RAM running DOS 5.0 with *Mathematica* 2.0 and *Windows* 3.1. The results from the session were copied to the clipboard and then pasted directly into *MS-Word* 2.0a.

$$pd \equiv \dot{p}.$$

We begin by defining the first stage of the transformation where the use of the semicolon-colon after an input line suppresses output for that particular line. The output is suppressed in these cases since Mathematica will reproduce what it was given as input.

In[2]:=

$$q1=q + h \text{ qd}[q,p];$$

In[3]:=

$$p1=p + h \text{ pd}[q,p];$$

We now define the final transformation given by (3.4.6) where we are using $qd1 \equiv \dot{q}'$ and $pd1 \equiv \dot{p}'$. We will also make the substitution $h \equiv \varepsilon$.

In[4]:=

$$Q=q + h/2 (\text{qd}[q,p]+\text{qd1}[q1,p1]);$$

In[5]:=

$$P=p + h/2 (\text{pd}[q,p]+\text{pd1}[q1,p1]);$$

In[6]:=

$$J1=\{\{D[q1,q],D[q1,p]\},\{D[p1,q],D[p1,p]\}\};$$

In the above input we have constructed the Jacobian matrix for the first stage of the transformation.

J1 is equivalent to

$$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial q'}{\partial q} & \frac{\partial q'}{\partial p} \\ \frac{\partial p'}{\partial q} & \frac{\partial p'}{\partial p} \end{pmatrix},$$

where $D[q1, q]$ is the Mathematica syntax for $\frac{\partial q'}{\partial q}$, etc.

In[7]:=

J={ {D[Q,q],D[Q,p]}, {D[P,q],D[P,p]}};

J is the Jacobian matrix for the final transformation.

In[8]:=

PoissonBracket1=Det[J1];

In[9]:=

PoissonBracket=Det[J];

Input lines (8) and (9) calculate the determinants of the respective Jacobian matrices giving the Poisson Brackets for the first stage and final transformation.

In[10]:=

pb1=Collect[PoissonBracket1,h];

```
ln[11]:=
```

```
pb=Collect [PoissonBracket, h];
```

Input lines (10) and (11) collect terms in powers of h for the two Poisson Brackets.

In what follows we calculate the derivatives used in the Jacobian matrices for purposes of reference and display.

```
ln[12]:=
```

```
d1=D [Q, q];
```

```
ln[13]:=
```

```
d2=D [P, p];
```

```
ln[14]:=
```

```
d3=D [P, q];
```

```
ln[15]:=
```

```
d4=D [Q, p];
```

Before we display the results we can shorten output considerably by clearing the definitions of q1 and p1 given in input lines (2) and (3) and then making symbolic substitutions using just q1 and p1 .

```
ln[16]:=
```

```
ClearAll [q1, p1];
```

```
In[17]:=
```

```
d1=d1/.{(p+h pd[q,p])->p1,(q+h qd[q,p])->q1};
```

```
In[18]:=
```

```
d2=d2/.{(p+h pd[q,p])->p1,(q+h qd[q,p])->q1};
```

```
In[19]:=
```

```
d3=d3/.{(p+h pd[q,p])->p1,(q+h qd[q,p])->q1};
```

```
In[20]:=
```

```
d4=d4/.{(p+h pd[q,p])->p1,(q+h qd[q,p])->q1};
```

Now we collect and simplify the results from above and display the derivatives. These are the equations given in (3.4.8). Derivatives in *Mathematica* output are designated with ordered pair superscripts between the function symbol and the function arguments in brackets. The ordered pair superscripts refer directly to the function arguments. The numbers appearing in the superscripts give the order of the partial derivatives. For example:

$$qd^{(1,0)}[q,p] \equiv \frac{\partial \dot{q}}{\partial q}$$

$$H^{(2,2)}[q,p] \equiv \frac{\partial^4 H}{\partial q^2 \partial p^2}$$

$$pd1^{(0,3)}[q,p] \equiv \frac{\partial^3 \dot{p}}{\partial p^3}.$$

```
In[21]:=
```

```
Collect[Expand[d1],h]
```

Out[21]:=

$$1 + h \left(\frac{q_d^{(1,0)} [q, p]}{2} + \frac{q_{d1}^{(1,0)} [q1, p1]}{2} \right) +$$
$$h^2 \left(\frac{q_{d1}^{(0,1)} [q1, p1] p_d^{(1,0)} [q, p]}{2} + \right.$$
$$\left. \frac{q_d^{(1,0)} [q, p] q_{d1}^{(1,0)} [q1, p1]}{2} \right)$$

In[22]:=

Collect [Expand[d2], h]

Out[22]:=

$$1 + h \left(\frac{p_d^{(0,1)} [q, p]}{2} + \frac{p_{d1}^{(0,1)} [q1, p1]}{2} \right) +$$
$$h^2 \left(\frac{p_d^{(0,1)} [q, p] p_{d1}^{(0,1)} [q1, p1]}{2} + \right.$$
$$\left. \frac{q_d^{(0,1)} [q, p] p_{d1}^{(1,0)} [q1, p1]}{2} \right)$$

In[23]:=

Collect [Expand[d3], h]

Out[23]:=

$$h \left(\frac{p_d^{(1,0)} [q, p]}{2} + \frac{p_{d1}^{(1,0)} [q1, p1]}{2} \right) +$$
$$h^2 \left(\frac{p_{d1}^{(0,1)} [q1, p1] p_d^{(1,0)} [q, p]}{2} + \right.$$

$$\frac{\text{pd1} \begin{matrix} (1,0) \\ [q1, p1] \end{matrix} \text{qd} \begin{matrix} (1,0) \\ [q, p] \end{matrix}}{2}$$

In[24]:=

Collect [Expand[d4],h]

Out[24]:=

$$h \left(\frac{\text{qd} \begin{matrix} (0,1) \\ [q, p] \end{matrix}}{2} + \frac{\text{qd1} \begin{matrix} (0,1) \\ [q1, p1] \end{matrix}}{2} \right) +$$

$$h \left(\frac{2 \text{pd} \begin{matrix} (0,1) \\ [q, p] \end{matrix} \text{qd1} \begin{matrix} (0,1) \\ [q1, p1] \end{matrix}}{2} + \right.$$

$$\left. \frac{\text{qd} \begin{matrix} (0,1) \\ [q, p] \end{matrix} \text{qd1} \begin{matrix} (1,0) \\ [q1, p1] \end{matrix}}{2} \right)$$

Now display the Poisson Bracket for the first stage:

In[25]:=

pb1

Out[25]:=

$$1 + h \left(\text{pd} \begin{matrix} (0,1) \\ [q, p] \end{matrix} + \text{qd} \begin{matrix} (1,0) \\ [q, p] \end{matrix} \right) +$$

$$h \left(-\text{qd} \begin{matrix} (0,1) \\ [q, p] \end{matrix} \text{pd} \begin{matrix} (1,0) \\ [q, p] \end{matrix} \right) +$$

$$\text{pd} \begin{matrix} (0,1) \\ [q, p] \end{matrix} \text{qd} \begin{matrix} (1,0) \\ [q, p] \end{matrix}$$

In[26]:=

pb=pb/.{(p+h pd[q,p])->p1,(q+h qd[q,p])->q1};

In[27]:=

Length[Expand[pb]]

Out[27]:=

27

Input line (27) first expands the result contained in pb and then uses the Length[] function to give the number of polynomial terms in the expression. The Length[] function is useful when working with long polynomials and can be used for determining what effect a particular substitution may have on a polynomial without displaying the entire result. The following line simplifies and displays the Poisson Bracket for the transformation in (3.4.6). This corresponds to (3.4.9) in the text. Notice that the definitions for Hamilton's equations have not yet been made.

In[28]:=

Simplify[pb]

Out[28]:=

$$\begin{aligned} & 1 + (h \text{pd}^{(0,1)}[q, p] + \text{pd1}^{(0,1)}[q1, p1] + \text{qd}^{(1,0)}[q, p] + \\ & \quad \text{qd1}^{(1,0)}[q1, p1])) / 2 + \\ & \text{h}^4 (-\text{qd}^{(0,1)}[q, p] \text{pd}^{(1,0)}[q, p]) + \\ & \quad \text{pd}^{(0,1)}[q, p] \text{qd}^{(1,0)}[q, p]) \\ & \quad (-\text{qd1}^{(0,1)}[q1, p1] \text{pd1}^{(1,0)}[q1, p1]) + \\ & \quad \text{pd1}^{(0,1)}[q1, p1] \text{qd1}^{(1,0)}[q1, p1])) / 4 + \\ & \text{h}^2 (2 \text{pd}^{(0,1)}[q, p] \text{pd1}^{(0,1)}[q1, p1] - \\ & \quad \text{qd}^{(0,1)}[q, p] \text{pd}^{(1,0)}[q, p] + \\ & \quad \text{qd1}^{(0,1)}[q1, p1] \text{pd}^{(1,0)}[q, p] + \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{qd}^{(0,1)} [q, p] \text{pd1}^{(1,0)} [q1, p1] - \\
& \text{qd1}^{(0,1)} [q1, p1] \text{pd1}^{(1,0)} [q1, p1] + \\
& \text{pd}^{(0,1)} [q, p] \text{qd}^{(1,0)} [q, p] + \\
& \text{pd1}^{(0,1)} [q1, p1] \text{qd}^{(1,0)} [q, p] + \\
& \text{pd}^{(0,1)} [q, p] \text{qd1}^{(1,0)} [q1, p1] + \\
& \text{pd1}^{(0,1)} [q1, p1] \text{qd1}^{(1,0)} [q1, p1] + \\
& 2 \text{qd}^{(1,0)} [q, p] \text{qd1}^{(1,0)} [q1, p1]) / 4 + \\
3 & \text{(h } (-\text{pd1}^{(0,1)} [q1, p1] \text{qd}^{(0,1)} [q, p] \text{pd}^{(1,0)} [q, p]) - \\
& \text{pd}^{(0,1)} [q, p] \text{qd1}^{(0,1)} [q1, p1] \text{pd1}^{(1,0)} [q1, p1] + \\
& \text{pd}^{(0,1)} [q, p] \text{pd1}^{(0,1)} [q1, p1] \text{qd}^{(1,0)} [q, p] - \\
& \text{qd1}^{(0,1)} [q1, p1] \text{pd1}^{(1,0)} [q1, p1] \text{qd}^{(1,0)} [q, p] + \\
& \text{pd}^{(0,1)} [q, p] \text{pd1}^{(0,1)} [q1, p1] \text{qd1}^{(1,0)} [q1, p1] - \\
& \text{qd}^{(0,1)} [q, p] \text{pd}^{(1,0)} [q, p] \text{qd1}^{(1,0)} [q1, p1] + \\
& \text{pd}^{(0,1)} [q, p] \text{qd}^{(1,0)} [q, p] \text{qd1}^{(1,0)} [q1, p1] + \\
& \text{pd1}^{(0,1)} [q1, p1] \text{qd}^{(1,0)} [q, p] \text{qd1}^{(1,0)} [q1, p1]) / 4
\end{aligned}$$

In[29]:=

Length[%]

Out{29}:=

5

Now we define and substitute Hamiltons Equations (3.4.1) into the Poisson Bracket for the first stage

In{30}:=

```
pb1=pb1/.{(D[pd[q,p],p])>>(D[H[q,p],q,p]),
           (D[qd[q,p],q])>>(D[H[q,p],q,p]),
           (D[pd[q,p],q])>>(D[H[q,p],q,q]),
           (D[qd[q,p],p])>>(D[H[q,p],p,p]) }
```

Out{30}:=

$$1 + h^2 \left(-H^{(1,1)}[q, p] + H^{(0,2)}[q, p] H^{(2,0)}[q, p] \right)$$

Output line (30) is the Poisson Bracket used in (3.4.7). Now define and substitute Hamilton's equations (3.4.1) into the Poisson Bracket:

In{31}:=

```
pb=pb/.{(D[pd[q,p],p])>>(D[H[q,p],q,p]),
          (D[qd[q,p],q])>>(D[H[q,p],q,p]),
          (D[pd[q,p],q])>>(D[H[q,p],q,q]),
          (D[qd[q,p],p])>>(D[H[q,p],p,p]) };
```

Define and substitute Hamiltons Equations (3.4.7) for the 1st stage:

In{32}:=

```
pb=pb/.{(D[pd1[q1,p1],p1])>>(D[pb1 H[q1,p1],q1,p1]),
          (D[qd1[q1,p1],q1])>>(D[pb1 H[q1,p1],q1,p1]),
          (D[pd1[q1,p1],q1])>>(D[pb1 H[q1,p1],q1,q1]),
          (D[qd1[q1,p1],p1])>>(D[pb1 H[q1,p1],p1,p1]) };
```

Give a list of all powers of h:

In{33}:=

```
Cases[Collect[pb,h],h^_,2]
```

Out[33]:=

$\{h^2, h^4, h^6, h^8\}$

In[34]:=

Simplify[Take[Collect[pb,h],4]]

Out[34]:=

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1 + (3 h^6 (-H^{(1,1)} [q, p]^2 + H^{(0,2)} [q, p] H^{(2,0)} [q, p])^2 \\
 & \quad (-H^{(1,1)} [q_1, p_1]^2 + H^{(0,2)} [q_1, p_1] H^{(2,0)} [q_1, p_1])) / 4 \setminus \\
 & + (h^2 (-H^{(1,1)} [q, p]^2 + 2 H^{(1,1)} [q, p] H^{(1,1)} [q_1, p_1] - \\
 & \quad H^{(1,1)} [q_1, p_1]^2 + H^{(0,2)} [q, p] H^{(2,0)} [q, p] - \\
 & \quad H^{(0,2)} [q_1, p_1] H^{(2,0)} [q, p] - \\
 & \quad H^{(0,2)} [q, p] H^{(2,0)} [q_1, p_1] + \\
 & \quad H^{(0,2)} [q_1, p_1] H^{(2,0)} [q_1, p_1])) / 4 + \\
 & (h^4 (-H^{(1,1)} [q, p]^2 + H^{(0,2)} [q, p] H^{(2,0)} [q, p]) \\
 & \quad (2 H^{(1,1)} [q, p] H^{(1,1)} [q_1, p_1] - 3 H^{(1,1)} [q_1, p_1]^2 - \\
 & \quad H^{(0,2)} [q_1, p_1] H^{(2,0)} [q, p] - \\
 & \quad H^{(0,2)} [q, p] H^{(2,0)} [q_1, p_1] + \\
 & \quad 3 H^{(0,2)} [q_1, p_1] H^{(2,0)} [q_1, p_1])) / 4
 \end{aligned}$$

Output line (34) is the result in (3.4.11).

Make a functional substitution for q' and p' so that they can be expanded as a series in h:

In[35]:=

pb=pb/.{q1->q1[h],p1->p1[h]};

Perform the series expansions (3.4.12) for the derivatives involving $H(q',p')$

```
In[36]:=
s1=Normal[ Series[D[H[q1[h],p1[h]],q1[h],p1[h]] ,{h,0,2} ]];
```

```
In[37]:=
s2=Normal[ Series[D[H[q1[h],p1[h]],p1[h],p1[h]] ,{h,0,2} ]];
```

```
In[38]:=
s3=Normal[ Series[D[H[q1[h],p1[h]],q1[h],q1[h]] ,{h,0,2} ]];
```

Now we simplify and collect s_1 , s_2 , and s_3 for purposes of display. The following results are contained in (3.4.12).

```
In[39]:=
```

```
Simplify[Collect[s1,h]]
```

```
Out[39]:=
```

$$\begin{aligned}
 & H^{(1,1)} [q1[0], p1[0]] + h \\
 & (p1'[0] H^{(1,2)} [q1[0], p1[0]] + q1'[0] H^{(2,1)} [q1[0], p1[0]]) \\
 & + (h^2 (p1''[0] H^{(1,2)} [q1[0], p1[0]] + \\
 & p1'[0] H^{(1,3)} [q1[0], p1[0]] + \\
 & q1''[0] H^{(2,1)} [q1[0], p1[0]] + \\
 & 2 p1'[0] q1'[0] H^{(2,2)} [q1[0], p1[0]] + \\
 & q1'[0] H^{(3,1)} [q1[0], p1[0]])) / 2
 \end{aligned}$$

```
In[40]:=
```

```
Simplify[Collect[s2,h]]
```

```
Out[40]:=
```

$$\begin{aligned}
 & H^{(0,2)} [q1[0], p1[0]] + h \\
 & (p1'[0] H^{(0,3)} [q1[0], p1[0]] + q1'[0] H^{(1,2)} [q1[0], p1[0]])
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + (h^2 (p1''[0] H^{(0,3)} [q1[0], p1[0]] + \\
& \quad p1'[0]^2 H^{(0,4)} [q1[0], p1[0]] + \\
& \quad q1''[0] H^{(1,2)} [q1[0], p1[0]] + \\
& \quad 2 p1'[0] q1'[0] H^{(1,3)} [q1[0], p1[0]] + \\
& \quad q1'[0]^2 H^{(2,2)} [q1[0], p1[0]])) / 2
\end{aligned}$$

In[41]:=

Simplify[Collect[s3,h]]

Out[41]:=

$$\begin{aligned}
& H^{(2,0)} [q1[0], p1[0]] + h \\
& (p1'[0] H^{(2,1)} [q1[0], p1[0]] + q1'[0] H^{(3,0)} [q1[0], p1[0]]) \\
& + (h^2 (p1''[0] H^{(2,1)} [q1[0], p1[0]] + \\
& \quad p1'[0]^2 H^{(2,2)} [q1[0], p1[0]] + \\
& \quad q1''[0] H^{(3,0)} [q1[0], p1[0]] + \\
& \quad 2 p1'[0] q1'[0] H^{(3,1)} [q1[0], p1[0]] + \\
& \quad q1'[0]^2 H^{(4,0)} [q1[0], p1[0]])) / 2
\end{aligned}$$

Substitute the series expansions into the Poisson Bracket

In[42]:=

```

pb=pb/.{ D[H[q1[h],p1[h]],q1[h],p1[h]] -> s1,
         D[H[q1[h],p1[h]],p1[h],p1[h]] -> s2,
         D[H[q1[h],p1[h]],q1[h],q1[h]] -> s3 };

```

Expand out the result.

In[43]:=

PB=ExpandAll[pb];

Count the number of polynomial terms in the expression:

In[44]:=

Length[PB]

Out[44]:=

915

Substitute the derivatives for the first stage with respect to h into the Poisson Bracket. These substitutions can be seen by inspection of input lines (2) and (3).

In[45]:=

PB=Pb/.{ p1'[0]->pd,q1'[0]->qd,q1[0]->q,p1[0]->p,
p1''[0]->0,q1''[0]->0};

Sort and collect the result in powers of h

In[46]:=

pb=Sort[Collect[PB,h]];

Give a list of all powers of h:

In[47]:=

Cases[pb,h^_,2]

Out[47]:=

{h⁴, h⁵, h⁷, h⁹, h¹¹, h⁶, h⁸, h¹⁰, h¹²}

In[48]:=

Simplify[Take[pb,2]]

Out[48]:=

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1 + (h^4 (H^{(1,1)} [q, p] - pd H^2 [q, p] - \\
& \quad 2 H^{(0,2)} [q, p] H^{(1,1)} [q, p] H^2 [q, p] + \\
& \quad H^{(0,2)} [q, p] H^2 [q, p] +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{pd } H^{(0,3)} [q, p] H^{(2,1)} [q, p] - \\
& \text{pd } qd H^{(1,2)} [q, p] H^{(2,1)} [q, p] - qd^2 H^{(2,1)} [q, p]^2 + \\
& \text{pd } qd H^{(0,3)} [q, p] H^{(3,0)} [q, p] + \\
& qd^2 H^{(1,2)} [q, p] H^{(3,0)} [q, p]) / 4
\end{aligned}$$

The above result is the final Poisson Bracket given in (3.4.13).

Next we start the calculations for the series expansion of $H(Q, P)$.

Clear the previous definitions for Q and P given in input lines (4) and (5):

In[49]:=

ClearAll [Q,P]

Generate a general power series for $H(Q,P)$, in h, about the point $h=0$ for three terms. This is (3.4.14).

In[50]:=

H1=Series [H [Q [h], P [h]], {h, 0, 3}]

Out[50]:=

$$\begin{aligned}
& H [Q [0], P [0]] + (P' [0] H^{(0,1)} [Q [0], P [0]] + \\
& Q' [0] H^{(1,0)} [Q [0], P [0]]) h + \\
& \left(\frac{P'' [0] H^{(0,1)} [Q [0], P [0]]}{2} + \frac{P' [0]^2 H^{(0,2)} [Q [0], P [0]]}{2} + \right. \\
& \left. \frac{Q'' [0] H^{(1,0)} [Q [0], P [0]]}{2} + \right. \\
& P' [0] Q' [0] H^{(1,1)} [Q [0], P [0]] + \\
& \left. \frac{Q' [0]^2 H^{(2,0)} [Q [0], P [0]]}{2} \right) h^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

2

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{(3) \quad (0,1)}{P \quad [0] \quad H \quad [Q[0], P[0]]} \\
 & \frac{P \quad [0] \quad H \quad [Q[0], P[0]]}{6} + \\
 & \frac{(0,2)}{P' [0] \quad P'' [0] \quad H \quad [Q[0], P[0]]} \\
 & \frac{P' [0] \quad P'' [0] \quad H \quad [Q[0], P[0]]}{2} + \\
 & \frac{3 \quad (0,3)}{P' [0] \quad H \quad [Q[0], P[0]]} + \frac{(3) \quad (1,0)}{Q \quad [0] \quad H \quad [Q[0], P[0]]} \\
 & \frac{P' [0] \quad H \quad [Q[0], P[0]]}{6} + \frac{Q \quad [0] \quad H \quad [Q[0], P[0]]}{6} + \\
 & \left(\frac{Q' [0] \quad P'' [0]}{2} + \frac{P' [0] \quad Q'' [0]}{2} \right) H \quad (1,1) \quad [Q[0], P[0]] + \\
 & \frac{2 \quad (1,2)}{P' [0] \quad Q' [0] \quad H \quad [Q[0], P[0]]} \\
 & \frac{P' [0] \quad Q' [0] \quad H \quad [Q[0], P[0]]}{2} + \\
 & \frac{(2,0)}{Q' [0] \quad Q'' [0] \quad H \quad [Q[0], P[0]]} \\
 & \frac{Q' [0] \quad Q'' [0] \quad H \quad [Q[0], P[0]]}{2} + \\
 & \frac{2 \quad (2,1)}{P' [0] \quad Q' [0] \quad H \quad [Q[0], P[0]]} \\
 & \frac{P' [0] \quad Q' [0] \quad H \quad [Q[0], P[0]]}{2} + \\
 & \frac{3 \quad (3,0)}{Q' [0] \quad H \quad [Q[0], P[0]]} \quad 3 \quad 4 \\
 & \frac{Q' [0] \quad H \quad [Q[0], P[0]]}{6} \quad h \quad + O[h]
 \end{aligned}$$

Define Hamiltons equations:

ln[51]:=

qd=D[H[q,p],p];

ln[52]:=

pd=-D[H[q,p],q];

Define the Transformation again

ln[53]:=

$$q1=q + h \ qd;$$

In[54]:=

$$p1=p + h \ pd;$$

In[55]:=

$$Q=q + h/2 \ (qd+qd1[q1,p1]);$$

In[56]:=

$$P=p + h/2 \ (pd+pd1[q1,p1]);$$

Calculate the derivatives for purposes of display that are substituted into (3.4.14):

In[57]:=

$$dQh=D [Q, h] ;$$

In[58]:=

$$dQh2=D [Q, h, h] ;$$

In[59]:=

$$dPh=D [P, h] ;$$

In[60]:=

$$dPh2=D [P, h, h] ;$$

Evaluate the above at h=0. The result is (3.4.15).

In[70]:=

$$dQh /. \{h \rightarrow 0\}$$

Out[70]:=

$$\frac{qd1[q, p] + H^{(0,1)}[q, p]}{2}$$

In[71]:=

$$dQh2 /. \{h \rightarrow 0\}$$

Out[71]:=

$$\begin{matrix} (0, 1) & (1, 0) & (0, 1) & (1, 0) \end{matrix}$$

```

-(qd1 [q, p] H [q, p]) + H [q, p] qd1 [q, p]
In[72]:=

```

```

dPh/.{h->0}

```

```

Out[72]:=

```

$$\frac{\text{pd1}[q, p] - H^{(1,0)}[q, p]}{2}$$

```

In[73]:=

```

```

dPh2/.{h->0}

```

```

Out[73]:=

```

$$-(\text{pd1}^{(0,1)}[q, p] H^{(1,0)}[q, p]) + H^{(0,1)}[q, p] \text{pd1}^{(1,0)}[q, p]$$

Generate a power series for $H(Q,P)$, in h , about the point $h=0$ using the transformation equations for Q and P .

```

In[74]:=

```

```

H1=Series[H[Q,P],{h,0,3}];

```

The following substitutions are equivalent to making the evaluations at $h=0$.

```

In[75]:=

```

```

H1=H1/.{ qd1[q,p]->qd,
         pd1[q,p]->pd };

```

```

In[76]:=

```

```

H1=H1/.{ D[qd1[q,p],q]->D[qd,q],
         D[qd1[q,p],p]->D[qd,p],
         D[pd1[q,p],q]->D[pd,q],
         D[pd1[q,p],p]->D[pd,p] };

```

```

In[77]:=

```

```

H1=H1/.{ D[qd1[q,p],q,q]->D[qd,q,q],
         D[qd1[q,p],p,q]->D[qd,p,q],
         D[pd1[q,p],q,q]->D[pd,q,q],
         D[pd1[q,p],p,q]->D[pd,p,q] };

```

```

In[78]:=

```

```

H1=H1/.{ D[qd1[q,p],q,p]->D[qd,q,p],
         D[qd1[q,p],p,p]->D[qd,p,p],

```

D[pd1[q,p],q,p]->D[pd,q,p],
D[pd1[q,p],p,p]->D[pd,p,p] };

Simplify and cancel common terms in the above:

In[79]:=

Simplify[H1]

Out[79]:=

$$\begin{aligned}
& H[q, p] + \left(H^{(0,3)}[q, p] H^{(1,0)}[q, p]^3 - \right. \\
& \quad 3 H^{(0,1)}[q, p] H^{(1,0)}[q, p]^2 H^{(1,2)}[q, p] + \\
& \quad \left. 3 H^{(0,1)}[q, p]^2 H^{(1,0)}[q, p] H^{(2,1)}[q, p] - \right. \\
& \quad \left. H^{(0,1)}[q, p]^3 H^{(3,0)}[q, p] \right) h^3 / 12 + O[h]^4
\end{aligned}$$

The above result is (3.4.16).

Appendix C Heun's Method

Here we give the text used as input to *Mathematica* for the calculations involving Heun's method. Due to the similarity with Appendix B many of the results will not be reproduced but in some cases the actual output is shown to indicate specific results given in the text.

Share common sub-expressions throughout memory

```
Share []
```

Set up the 1st Stage of the Transformation

```
q1=q + 2h/3 qd[q,p];
```

```
p1=p + 2h/3 pd[q,p];
```

These are the Transformation Equations

```
Q=q + h/4 (qd[q,p] + 3 qd1[q1,p1]);
```

```
P=p + h/4 (pd[q,p] + 3 pd1[q1,p1]);
```

Construct the Jacobian Matrix for the first stage of the transformation

```
J1={{D[q1,q],D[q1,p]},{D[p1,q],D[p1,p]}};
```

Construct the Jacobian Matrix for the final transformation

```
J={{D[Q,q],D[Q,p]},{D[P,q],D[P,p]}};
```

Calculate the Determinants of the Jacobian Matrices (Poisson Brackets) for the first and final stage of the transformation

```
PoissonBracket1=Det [J1];
```

```
PoissonBracket=Det [J];
```

Collect terms in powers of h for the two Poisson Brackets

```
pb1=Collect [PoissonBracket1, h];
```

```
pb=Collect [PoissonBracket, h];
```

Calculate Derivatives used to form the Poisson Bracket

```
d1=Simplify [Collect [D [Q, q], h]];
```

```
d2=Simplify [Collect [D [P, p], h]];
```

```
d3=Simplify [Collect [D [P, q], h]];
```

```
d4=Simplify [Collect [D [Q, p], h]];
```

Clear the definitions for the 1st stage and make symbolic substitutions

```
ClearAll [q1, p1];
```

```
d1=d1/. {(p+2h/3 pd[q, p]) -> p1, (q+2h/3 qd[q, p]) -> q1};
```

```
d2=d2/. {(p+2h/3 pd[q, p]) -> p1, (q+2h/3 qd[q, p]) -> q1};
```

```
d3=d3/. {(p+2h/3 pd[q, p]) -> p1, (q+2h/3 qd[q, p]) -> q1};
```

```
d4=d4/. {(p+2h/3 pd[q, p]) -> p1, (q+2h/3 qd[q, p]) -> q1};
```

Display the derivatives (3.4.20)

```
Collect [Expand [d1], h]
```

```
Collect [Expand [d2], h]
```

```
Collect [Expand [d3], h]
```

Collect [Expand[d4],h]

Display the Poisson Bracket for the first stage (used in (3.4.19))

pb1;

Display the Poisson Bracket for the final transformation (3.4.22)

pb=pb/.{(p+2h/3 pd[q,p])->p1,(q+2h/3 qd[q,p])->q1};

Define and substitute Hamiltons Equations (3.4.1) into the Poisson Bracket for the first stage

pb1=pb1/.{(D[pd[q,p],p])->(D[H[q,p],q,p]),
(D[qd[q,p],q])->(D[H[q,p],q,p]),
(D[pd[q,p],q])->(D[H[q,p],q,q]),
(D[qd[q,p],p])->(D[H[q,p],p,p])};

Define and substitute Hamiltons Equations (3.4.1) into the Poisson Bracket

pb=pb/.{(D[pd[q,p],p])->(D[H[q,p],q,p]),
(D[qd[q,p],q])->(D[H[q,p],q,p]),
(D[pd[q,p],q])->(D[H[q,p],q,q]),
(D[qd[q,p],p])->(D[H[q,p],p,p])};

Define and substitute Hamiltons Equations (3.4.19) for the 1st stage

pb=pb/.{(D[pd1[q1,p1],p1])->(D[pb1 H[q1,p1],q1,p1]),
(D[qd1[q1,p1],q1])->(D[pb1 H[q1,p1],q1,p1]),
(D[pd1[q1,p1],q1])->(D[pb1 H[q1,p1],q1,q1]),
(D[qd1[q1,p1],p1])->(D[pb1 H[q1,p1],p1,p1])};

Give a list of all powers of h

```
Cases[Collect[pb,h],h^_,2]
```

```
  2   4   6   8
{h , h , h , h }
```

This is (3.4.22)

```
Simplify[Collect [pb,h]];
```

Make a functional substitution for q' and p' so that they can be expanded as a series in h

```
pb=pb/. {q1->q1 [h],p1->p1 [h]};
```

Perform the series expansions (3.4.12) for the derivatives involving H(q',p')

```
s1=Normal[ Series[D[H[q1 [h],p1 [h]],q1 [h],p1 [h]] ,{h,0,2}] ];
```

```
s2=Normal[ Series[D[H[q1 [h],p1 [h]],p1 [h],p1 [h]] ,{h,0,2}] ];
```

```
s3=Normal[ Series[D[H[q1 [h],p1 [h]],q1 [h],q1 [h]] ,{h,0,2}] ];
```

Substitute the series expansions into the Poisson Bracket

```
pb=pb/. { D[H[q1 [h],p1 [h]],q1 [h],p1 [h]] -> s1,
```

```
pb=pb/. { D[H[q1 [h],p1 [h]],p1 [h],p1 [h]] -> s2,
```

```
pb=pb/. { D[H[q1 [h],p1 [h]],q1 [h],q1 [h]] -> s3 };
```

Expand out the result

```
PB=Expand[pb];
```

Count the number of polynomial terms in the expression

```
Length[PB]
```

```
915
```

Substitute the derivatives for the first stage with respect to h into the Poisson Bracket

```
PB=PB/.{ p1'[0]->pd,q1'[0]->qd,q1[0]->q,p1[0]->p,
        p1''[0]->0,q1''[0]->0 };
```

```
Length[PB]
```

```
453
```

Collect in powers of h

```
pb=Sort[Collect[PB,h]];
```

Give a list of all powers of h

```
Cases[pb,h^_,2]
```

```
  3  4  5  7  9  11  6  8  10  12
{h , h , h , h , h , h , h , h , h , h }
```

This is the final Poisson Bracket result (3.4.25)

```
Simplify[Take[pb,2]]
```

$$\begin{aligned}
 1 + & h^3 (-2 \text{pd} H^{(1,1)} [q, p] H^{(1,2)} [q, p] + \\
 & \text{pd} H^{(0,3)} [q, p] H^{(2,0)} [q, p] + \\
 & \text{qd} H^{(1,2)} [q, p] H^{(2,0)} [q, p] + \\
 & \text{pd} H^{(0,2)} [q, p] H^{(2,1)} [q, p] - \\
 & 2 \text{qd} H^{(1,1)} [q, p] H^{(2,1)} [q, p] +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$qd = \frac{H^{(0,2)}[q, p] + H^{(3,0)}[q, p]}{4}$$

Start the Calculations for the series expansion of $H(Q,P)$

Clear the definitions for Q and P

ClearAll [Q,P]

Define Hamiltons equations

qd=D [H [q,p] ,p];

pd=-D [H [q,p] ,q];

Define the Transformation again

q1=q + 2h/3 qd;

p1=p + 2h/3 pd;

Q=q + h/4 (qd + 3 qd1 [q1,p1]);

P=p + h/4 (pd + 3 pd1 [q1,p1]);

Calculate the derivatives that are substituted into (3.4.14)

dQh=D [Q, h];

dQh2=D [Q, h, h];

dPh=D [P, h];

dPh2=D [P, h, h];

Evaluate the above at $h=0$

dQh/. {h->0}

dQh2/. {h->0}

dPh/. {h->0}

dPh2/. {h->0}

Generate a power series for $H(Q,P)$, in h , about the point $h=0$ using the transformation equations for Q and P .

H1=Series[H[Q,P], {h, 0, 3}];

The following substitutions are equivalent to making the evaluations at $h=0$.

H1=H1/. { qd1[q,p]->qd,
pd1[q,p]->pd };

H1=H1/. { D[qd1[q,p],q]->D[qd,q],
D[qd1[q,p],p]->D[qd,p],
D[pd1[q,p],q]->D[pd,q],
D[pd1[q,p],p]->D[pd,p] };

H1=H1/. { D[qd1[q,p],q,q]->D[qd,q,q],
D[qd1[q,p],p,q]->D[qd,p,q],
D[pd1[q,p],q,q]->D[pd,q,q],
D[pd1[q,p],p,q]->D[pd,p,q] };

H1=H1/. { D[qd1[q,p],q,p]->D[qd,q,p],
D[qd1[q,p],p,p]->D[qd,p,p],
D[pd1[q,p],q,p]->D[pd,q,p],
D[pd1[q,p],p,p]->D[pd,p,p] };

Simplify and cancel common terms (3.4.26)
Simplify[H1]

H[q, p] + O[h]⁴

Appendix D The Midpoint Method

Share common sub-expressions throughout memory

```
Share []
```

Set up the 1st Stage of the Transformation

```
q1=q + h/2 qd[q,p];
```

```
p1=p + h/2 pd[q,p];
```

These are the Transformation Equations

```
Q=q + h qd1[q1,p1];
```

```
P=p + h pd1[q1,p1];
```

Construct the Jacobian Matrix for the first stage of the transformation

```
J1={{D[q1,q],D[q1,p]},{D[p1,q],D[p1,p]}};
```

Construct the Jacobian Matrix for the final transformation

```
J={{D[Q,q],D[Q,p]},{D[P,q],D[P,p]}};
```

Calculate the Determinants of the Jacobian Matrices (Poisson Brackets) for the first and final stage of the transformation

```
PoissonBracket1=Det[J1];
```

```
PoissonBracket=Det[J];
```

Collect terms in powers of h for the two Poisson Brackets

```
pb1=Collect[PoissonBracket1,h];
```

```
pb=Collect [PoissonBracket, h];
```

Calculate Derivatives used to form the Poisson Bracket (3.4.31)

```
d1=Simplify[Collect [D [Q, q], h]];
d2=Simplify[Collect [D [P, p], h]];
d3=Simplify[Collect [D [P, q], h]];
d4=Simplify[Collect [D [Q, p], h]];

```

Clear the definitions for the 1st stage and make symbolic substitutions

```
ClearAll [q1, p1];
```

```
d1=d1/.{(p+h/2 pd[q,p])->p1, (q+h/2 qd[q,p])->q1};
d2=d2/.{(p+h/2 pd[q,p])->p1, (q+h/2 qd[q,p])->q1};
d3=d3/.{(p+h/2 pd[q,p])->p1, (q+h/2 qd[q,p])->q1};
d4=d4/.{(p+h/2 pd[q,p])->p1, (q+h/2 qd[q,p])->q1};

```

Display the derivatives (3.4.31)

```
Collect [Expand [d1], h]
```

```
Collect [Expand [d2], h]
```

```
Collect [Expand [d3], h]
```

```
Collect [Expand [d4], h]
```

Display the Poisson Bracket for the first stage (3.4.29)

```
pb1
```

Display the Poisson Bracket for the final transformation (3.4.32)

```
pb=pb/.{(p+h/2 pd[q,p])->p1, (q+h/2 qd[q,p])->q1};
```

Define and substitute Hamiltons Equations (3.4.1) into the Poisson Bracket for the first stage

```
pb1=pb1/.{(D[pd[q,p],p])-->(D[H[q,p],q,p]),
          (D[qd[q,p],q])->(D[H[q,p],q,p]),
          (D[pd[q,p],q])-->(D[H[q,p],q,q]),
          (D[qd[q,p],p])->(D[H[q,p],p,p])};
```

Define and substitute Hamiltons Equations (3.4.1) into the Poisson Bracket

```
pb=pb/.{(D[pd[q,p],p])-->(D[H[q,p],q,p]),
          (D[qd[q,p],q])->(D[H[q,p],q,p]),
          (D[pd[q,p],q])-->(D[H[q,p],q,q]),
          (D[qd[q,p],p])->(D[H[q,p],p,p])};
```

Define and substitute Hamiltons Equations (3.4.30) for the 1st stage

```
pb=pb/.{(D[pd1[q1,p1],p1])-->(D[pb1 H[q1,p1],q1,p1]),
          (D[qd1[q1,p1],q1])->(D[pb1 H[q1,p1],q1,p1]),
          (D[pd1[q1,p1],q1])-->(D[pb1 H[q1,p1],q1,q1]),
          (D[qd1[q1,p1],p1])->(D[pb1 H[q1,p1],p1,p1])};
```

Give a list of all powers of h

```
Cases[Collect[pb,h],h^_,2]
```

```
  2   4   6   8
{h , h , h , h }
```

This is (3.4.33)

```
Simplify[Collect[pb,h]];
```

Make a functional substitution for q' and p' so that they can be expanded as a series in h

```
pb=pb/.{q1->q1[h],p1->p1[h]};
```

Perform the series expansions (3.4.12) for the derivatives involving H(q',p')

```
s1=Normal[ Series[D[H[q1[h],p1[h]],q1[h],p1[h]] ,{h,0,2}] ];
```

```
s2=Normal[ Series[D[H[q1[h],p1[h]],p1[h],p1[h]] ,{h,0,2}] ];
```

```
s3=Normal[ Series[D[H[q1[h],p1[h]],q1[h],q1[h]] ,{h,0,2}] ];
```

Substitute the series expansions into the Poisson Bracket

```
pb=pb/.{ D[H[q1[h],p1[h]],q1[h],p1[h]] -> s1,
```

```
pb=pb/.{ D[H[q1[h],p1[h]],p1[h],p1[h]] -> s2,
```

```
pb=pb/.{ D[H[q1[h],p1[h]],q1[h],q1[h]] -> s3 };
```

Expand out the result

```
PB=Expand[pb];
```

Count the number of polynomial terms in the expression

```
Length[PB]
```

```
913
```

Substitute the derivatives for the first stage with respect to h into the Poisson Bracket

```
PB=PB/.{ p1'[0]->pd,q1'[0]->qd,q1[0]->q,p1[0]->p,
```

```
p1''[0]->0,q1''[0]->0 };
```

Count the number of polynomial terms in the expression

```
Length[PB]
```

453

Collect in powers of h

```
pb=Sort [Collect [PB,h]];
```

Give a list of all powers of h

```
Cases [pb,h^_,2]
```

```
  3   4   5   7   9   11   6   8   10   12  
{h , h , h , h , h , h , h , h , h , h }
```

This is the final Poisson Bracket result (3.4.13)

```
Simplify[Take [pb,2]]
```

$$\begin{aligned} 1 + & (h^3 (-2 \text{pd } H^{(1,1)} [q, p] H^{(1,2)} [q, p] + \\ & \text{pd } H^{(0,3)} [q, p] H^{(2,0)} [q, p] + \\ & \text{qd } H^{(1,2)} [q, p] H^{(2,0)} [q, p] + \\ & \text{pd } H^{(0,2)} [q, p] H^{(2,1)} [q, p] - \\ & 2 \text{qd } H^{(1,1)} [q, p] H^{(2,1)} [q, p] + \\ & \text{qd } H^{(0,2)} [q, p] H^{(3,0)} [q, p])) / 2 \end{aligned}$$

Start the Calculations for the series expansion of $H(Q,P)$

Clear the definitions for Q and P

```
ClearAll [Q,P]
```

Define Hamiltons equations

$$q_d = D[H[q, p], p];$$

$$p_d = -D[H[q, p], q];$$

Define the Transformation again

$$q_1 = q + h/2 q_d;$$

$$p_1 = p + h/2 p_d;$$

$$Q = q + h q_{d1}[q_1, p_1];$$

$$P = p + h p_{d1}[q_1, p_1];$$

Calculate the derivatives that are substituted into (3.4.14)

$$dQh = D[Q, h];$$

$$dQh2 = D[Q, h, h];$$

$$dPh = D[P, h];$$

$$dPh2 = D[P, h, h];$$

Evaluate the above at h=0

$$dQh /. \{h \rightarrow 0\}$$

$$dQh2 /. \{h \rightarrow 0\}$$

$$dPh /. \{h \rightarrow 0\}$$

$$dPh2 /. \{h \rightarrow 0\}$$

Generate a power series for $H(Q,P)$, in h , about the point $h=0$ using the transformation equations for Q and P .

$$H1 = \text{Series}[H[Q, P], \{h, 0, 3\}];$$

The following substitutions are equivalent to making the evaluations at $h=0$.

$$H1 = H1 /. \{ \text{qd1}[q, p] \rightarrow \text{qd}, \\ \text{pd1}[q, p] \rightarrow \text{pd} \};$$

$$H1 = H1 /. \{ D[\text{qd1}[q, p], q] \rightarrow D[\text{qd}, q], \\ D[\text{qd1}[q, p], p] \rightarrow D[\text{qd}, p], \\ D[\text{pd1}[q, p], q] \rightarrow D[\text{pd}, q], \\ D[\text{pd1}[q, p], p] \rightarrow D[\text{pd}, p] \};$$

$$H1 = H1 /. \{ D[\text{qd1}[q, p], q, q] \rightarrow D[\text{qd}, q, q], \\ D[\text{qd1}[q, p], p, q] \rightarrow D[\text{qd}, p, q], \\ D[\text{pd1}[q, p], q, q] \rightarrow D[\text{pd}, q, q], \\ D[\text{pd1}[q, p], p, q] \rightarrow D[\text{pd}, p, q] \};$$

$$H1 = H1 /. \{ D[\text{qd1}[q, p], q, p] \rightarrow D[\text{qd}, q, p], \\ D[\text{qd1}[q, p], p, p] \rightarrow D[\text{qd}, p, p], \\ D[\text{pd1}[q, p], q, p] \rightarrow D[\text{pd}, q, p], \\ D[\text{pd1}[q, p], p, p] \rightarrow D[\text{pd}, p, p] \};$$

Simplify and cancel common terms (3.4.35)

Simplify[H1]

$$H[q, p] + ((- (H^{(0,3)}[q, p] H^{(1,0)}[q, p])^3 + \\ 3 H^{(0,1)}[q, p] H^{(1,0)}[q, p]^2 H^{(1,2)}[q, p] - \\ 3 H^{(0,1)}[q, p]^2 H^{(1,0)}[q, p] H^{(2,1)}[q, p] + \\ H^{(0,1)}[q, p]^3 H^{(3,0)}[q, p])^3 h^3) / 24 + O[h]^4$$

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